

ATLAS

ATLAS
Tourism and Leisure
Review

ASSOCIATION FOR TOURISM AND LEISURE RESEARCH
AND LEISURE EDUCATION

Volume 2026 – 1
ISSN 2468 – 6719

ATLAS Tourism and Leisure Review
Volume 2026 – 1
Creativity, Economy and Tourism

The Association for Tourism and Leisure Education and Research (ATLAS) was established in 1991 to develop transnational educational initiatives in tourism and leisure. ATLAS provides a forum to promote staff and student exchange, transnational research and to facilitate curriculum and professional development. ATLAS currently has members in about 50 countries. More information about ATLAS can be found at <http://www.atlas-euro.org/>.

The ATLAS Tourism and Leisure Review gives ATLAS members and participants of the ATLAS conferences and meetings a platform to publish the papers they have presented. The editing will be carried out by an editorial board / field editors.

ISSN 2468 – 6719

The ATLAS Tourism and Leisure Review will be distributed to ATLAS members for free.

ATLAS
PO Box 109
6800 AC Arnhem
The Netherlands
E-mail: info@atlas-euro.org

ATLAS Tourism and Leisure Review
Volume 2026 – 1
Creativity, Economy and Tourism

Field editor

René van der Duim – Wageningen University & Research, the Netherlands

Editorial board

Jim Butcher – Canterbury Christ Church University, United Kingdom

Corné Dijkmans – Breda University of Applied Sciences, Netherlands

René van der Duim – Wageningen University & Research, the Netherlands

Tara Duncan – Thompson Rivers University, Canada

Rose McBean – Breda University of Applied Sciences, Netherlands

Francis McGettigan – Athlone Institute of Technology, Ireland

Greg Richards –BUAS Breda University of Applied Sciences, Netherlands

Antonio Paolo Russo – University Rovira i Virgili, Spain

Ilja Simons – Breda University of Applied Sciences, Netherlands

Melanie Smith – Budapest University of Economics and Business, Hungary

**ATLAS Tourism and Leisure Review
Volume 2026 – 1
Creativity, Economy and Tourism**

Content

Introduction	5
Liability of Newness in Creative Economy: Environmental Conditions and the Role of Family Protection to Business	7
<i>Pablo Peron de Paula, Felipe Fróes Couto, Cledinaldo Aparecido Dias, Magnus Luiz Emmendoerfer</i>	
Creative economy and tourism: Mapping of enterprises and tourist routes in Grão Mogol	20
<i>Pablo Peron de Paula</i>	
Voluntourism Stakeholder Analysis	35
<i>Markos Psoras, Theodoros Stavrinoudis</i>	
Bridging international and social entrepreneurship in tourism. Case, the ViaVia Travelers Cafés.	52
<i>Dominique Vanneste, Jazmin Cevallos Vintimilla</i>	
What is ATLAS	74

Introduction

René van der Duim
Wageningen University & Research
The Netherlands

In this issue of ATLAS Review of Tourism and Leisure, we are glad to present four papers from our 2024 *Conference Leisure & Tourism 2030: Navigating the Future* hosted by Breda University of Applied Sciences. This conference brought together researchers, educators and innovators to explore the future of leisure and tourism, and how we can adapt to meet the changing landscape.

The four papers in the Volume deal with interfaces between culture and creativity, economy and/or tourism. In the first paper, Pablo Peron de Paula, Felipe Fróes Couto, Cleinaldo Aparecido Dias and Magnus Luiz Emmendoerfer demonstrate how the Liability of Newness (LoN) of creative businesses imposes the primary barriers to the development of new creative businesses in the municipality of Grão-Mogol, State of Minas Gerais, Brazil. The authors found profound and unexpected dimensions in the relationship between culture and economy. If, on the one hand, the application of the LoN model found a scenario conducive to the failure of creative businesses, on the other hand, the cultural and social environment of the place demonstrated that businesses can survive without the need to be profitable, since the moral value behind such ventures are others than accumulation.

In the second paper, Pablo Peron de Paula also examines creative economy enterprises in the municipality of Grão Mogol (Brazil) and how they support the tourist potential of the municipality by providing tourist routes that connect the natural beauties, the built cultural heritage, gastronomy, and handicrafts. The reserach project included mapping of the entire extension of the municipality, collecting geographic coordinates, in addition to conducting semi-structured interviews to diagnose the vulnerabilities and perception of potential attractions and local challenges. Through the mapping, about 60 points related to tourism and creative economy were identified. The semi-structured interviews, in turn, showed the recognition of the local tourism potential by the interviewees. However, there are a number of difficulties faced, related to the management of their activities, little institutional support, and absence of specific public policies. In view of the lack of consolidation of tourism in the region, the creation of tourist routes that interconnect the attractions was proposed, enabling the tourist to experience immersion, learning, and connection with nature and the local community. It is expected that the proposed itineraries will boost tourism activities, economic development, and the quality of life of the resident population.

In the third paper Psoras, Markos and Theodoros Stavrinoudis from Greece systematically identify the stakeholders in voluntourism by defining the type, role and responsibilities of each group. Using content analysis and stakeholder mapping, they evaluate the impact and interdependence of these actors. The results are synthesized into a stakeholder analysis matrix, followed by a stakeholder map, which visualizes the dynamic interdependencies and flows of

influence between the key stakeholders. The scientific contribution of this paper is the systematic categorization of key stakeholders, providing a structural framework to better understand the global voluntourism landscape.

The goal of the research of Dominique Vanneste and Jazmin Cevallos Vintimilla from the University of Leuven in Belgium was to identify how tourism social entrepreneurship (TSE) can relate to aspects of sustainable development and the links with the profile of the international investor. Their case brings an organization called ViaVia Travelers Cafés to the front. While originally stemming from Belgium, the ViaVia network has expanded to 18 different places anno 2024, thereby showing its success as one of the few SEs that scaled worldwide. This organization where, at the core, sustainable tourism and intercultural entrepreneurship meet, is an interesting example, although not without challenges. The lessons learned originate from an in-depth analysis of ViaVia León, situated in Nicaragua, where face-to-face information and experiences were exchanged with several stakeholders (manager, staff, locals, visitors etc.). But, for the sake of some generalization, the findings for ViaVia León were checked with several managers of ViaVia Cafés worldwide.

Liability of Newness in Creative Economy: Environmental Conditions and the Role of Family Protection to Business¹

*Pablo Peron de Paula
Felipe Fróes Couto
Cledinaldo Aparecido Dias
State University of Montes Claros
Brasil*

*Magnus Luiz Emmendoerfer
Universidade Federal de Viçosa
Brasil*

Introduction

This study begins by stating that the Liability of Newness (LoN) framework (Stinchcombe, 1965), while useful, needs to be considered in light of the specific socio-cultural context of the study area. We argue that the family plays a critical role in mitigating the challenges of LoN and that the local understanding of economic development prioritizes quality of life over accumulation. This argument emerges from the fact that the cultural dimension of society constitutes a field of rights that concerns the ways that people express themselves, create, and disseminate their humanity, and is related to the preservation of a language, customs, traditions, and identity (Costa, 2008). To speak of culture is to speak of the right that every human being has to socialize in their own environment, acquire their original identity and actively participate in public life (Cavalcante, 2014). For this reason, it is essential to recognize that the cultural field warrants significant discussion in the context of public policies, whether in the realm of human rights or economics (Leitão, 2016).

The economic sustainability of cultural production and the dynamics of the free market have led to a pragmatic view in which, although culture is recognized as a human right, it is also subject to market laws of supply and demand, transforming it into a consumption policy where producers act as suppliers and the general population as consumers (Bolaño et al., 2016). This perspective gave rise to the notion of the creative economy, where the concept of 'cultural life' was transformed into 'cultural goods' that could be mass-produced, thereby generating jobs, income, and economic development (Schlesinger, 2019). With the evolution of capitalism, especially in the post-industrial and post-Fordist context, 'creativity' has gained prominence as a central production factor, particularly as mechanical labor

¹ Acknowledgments to the Brazilian National Council of Technological and Scientific Development (CNPq), the Minas Gerais State Research Foundation (FAPEMIG), the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES), Ministry of Education, Brazil – Finance Code 001, and the Unesco Chair in Creative Economy & Public Policies. Additional thanks to Rose de Vrieze-McBean (Breda University of Applied Sciences) and the editorial staff of ATLAS Review for their valuable contributions to the improvement of this paper.

becomes increasingly automated (Silva, Vieira & Franco, 2019). In this scenario, beyond technological advancements, the future appears to be deeply cultural, emphasizing the content consumed online and through social media, with creativity becoming the core source of value generation in 21st-century capitalism (Paglioto, 2016). Consequently, the professionalization of cultural activities is now evident in a structured market, ranging from event production to the formalization of fields such as gastronomy and handicrafts, with cultural content production emerging as a major driver of wealth generation in contemporary capitalism (Machado, 2016).

Culture and creativity are now recognized as key sources of innovation, identifying new markets and facilitating expansion into emerging business opportunities. The language of business, in this sense, has appropriated the cultural field, so that artists, artisans, and creative professionals today find themselves vulnerable to market issues, clientele structuring, financial management, human resources, and legitimacy to operate in their respective markets (Alves & Souza, 2012). On the other hand, some studies related to cultural workers – especially those from rudimentary segments – reveal that there is still resistance concerning the commercialized view of culture, since the artist's work imprints its identity on his product, thus refusing the alienation of serial work and capitalist accumulation derived from creativity (Costa & Souza-Santos, 2012; Pacheco & Benini, 2018).

The emergence of these businesses goes through several market barriers, especially about the issue of copyright, decentralized markets (with a wide variety of producers), lack of public policies and precarious work (Almeida & Teixeira, 2016). Small producers are threatened by large oligopolies capable of dominating the control of cultural production, financed especially by economic groups interested in spreading their social values and ideal ways of building society, such as, for example, in the case of large film productions, which can create constraints for independent audiovisual productions (Santos & Davel, 2022).

In this paper, we seek to answer the following question: *Which internal and external aspects of the creative businesses' Liability of Newness impose the main barriers to the development of new ventures in the municipality of Grão-Mogol, State of Minas Gerais, Brazil?* Grão-Mogol is a municipality of approximately 14,000 inhabitants, whose urban perimeter is situated on a plateau at an altitude of 829m. The municipality, economically depressed, is mostly characterized by a rudimentary and agricultural economy. It is situated in a transitional region between the semi-arid and cerrado regions, experiencing drought and dryness from the end of autumn to the beginning of spring (Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística [IBGE], 2024).

This city is relevant because, in this research, we analyze a pre-federal intervention context for public policies on tourism and creative economy. In 2023, the "Cordilheira do Espinhaço" project was launched, which comprises the municipalities of Grão-Mogol, Itacambira, Caçaratiba (district of Turmalina), Cristália and Botumirim. It is an initiative to enhance the region as a tourist destination with its own identity and visual brand. The general idea behind the project would be to generate employment and income possibilities through ecotourism, offering training for small businesses that operate throughout the

destination, qualification of service providers (such as local tour guides) and consulting and managerial service to hotels, inns, restaurants, artisans and other enterprises that make up the tourism chain in the region (Agência Minas, 2023).

In this research, we found a rich (and complex) scenario. Through an exploratory and descriptive approach, we interviewed local cultural entrepreneurs to identify the main factors associated with the LoN. However, the case study revealed several layers of social and family organic relationships in the initial survival of creative businesses.

Liability of newness in the rudimentary creative economy

The 'creative economy' concept derives from a British movement to capitalize on culture, structured from the statement that creativity is an inexhaustible source of business and wealth (Moraes, 2018). The artisanal idea of culture is progressively replaced by a professionalization of the artist, alienating him from his origins and autonomy (Fioravante & Emmendoerfer, 2019), and creating an industry that standardizes, assigns scale, and massifies cultural consumption. The justification attributed to such a movement lies in the rationale that creative industries generate jobs and income. The field of creative economy, as a whole, encompasses eight major subfields: 1) *cultural heritage*, such as handicrafts, gastronomy, cultural expressions, and festivals; 2) *dramatic arts*, such as music, theater, and dance; 3) *audiovisual*, such as film, television, and radio; 4) *creative services*, such as architecture and advertising; 5) *new media*, such as games and software; 6) *fashion design*, interior, jewelry, etc.; 7) *publishing and print media*, such as books and press; and 8) *visual arts*, such as painting, sculpture and photography (Meleiro & Fonseca, 2018).

Newly created enterprises in this field face significant challenges to adapt, gain legitimacy before stakeholders and acquire the resources and skills necessary for their survival. The ordinary (daily) management of these 'new ventures' assumes the entrepreneur's conception of their enterprise. Previous research has shown that businesses in the field of rudimentary (non-technological) creative economy are characterized by more sustainable relationships with the natural environment, with a significant transfer of the artist's identity to their products (Wright, 2018). In addition, it was identified that, normally, there is no management structured by planning and formal organization of the productive activity (Almeida, Dias & Santos, 2021). Finally, a large scenario of work vulnerability was identified, without basic rights and guarantee of decent subsistence conditions (Comunian & England, 2020; Haubrich et al., 2020).

Because of this, part of these new businesses cannot achieve the goal of keeping operating. This phenomenon, initially identified by Stinchcombe (1965), was called "Liability of Newness" (LoN). Stinchcombe (1965) suggested that, in general, a higher proportion of new organizations tend to fail than older ones, and argued that these emerging organizations face complex obstacles that compromise their viability, such as managing relationships with unknown individuals, obtaining resources quickly, and navigating challenging environments.

For Stinchcombe, older companies have already established relationships and gained legitimacy with their stakeholders, while new ones face greater difficulties in gaining the necessary support. In addition, unlike established firms, new firms need to familiarize themselves with laws and regulations (Aldrich & Auster, 1986). The idea of "Liability of Newness" has established itself as a central concept to explain the difficulties and higher failure rates faced by new companies (DeVaughn & Leary, 2018).

Then, new enterprises should learn how to develop competencies to effectively engage relevant stakeholders (DeVaughn & Leary, 2018) and gain legitimacy with key resource groups such as investors, customers, and suppliers (Suchman, 1995). The component of personal loyalty in the relationship between consumer and producer is more difficult to build by new organizations, which can make it difficult for them to enter the market (Stinchcombe, 1965).

Figure 1: Factors that make up the Liability of Newness
Source: Stinchcombe (1965)

The factors that contribute to the LoN can be divided into internal and external. Among the internal factors, there are the absence of organizational routines, the need to establish new roles and the need for organizational learning. Among the external factors, stand out the difficulty of accessing non-financial strategic resources, the difficulty of building relationships with stakeholders and the lack of familiarity with rules, regulations and laws (Figure 1).

Among the challenges related to the "Liability of Newness" (LoN) are the need to understand the business environment and gain legitimacy (Wiklund et al., 2010). Legitimacy can be defined as the widespread perception or assumption that an organization's actions are desirable and appropriate within a socially constructed system of norms, values, and beliefs (Suchman, 1995). Entrepreneurs need to establish both their own legitimacy as founders and that of the new venture in order to be able to access resources they lack, such as funding, employees, suppliers, customer demand, and government approvals (Zhang & White, 2016).

By gaining legitimacy with stakeholders, entrepreneurs can considerably reduce obstacles in the early stages of their business (Winborg, 2015). While new businesses may achieve a good level of internal coherence, presenting a consistent image to external stakeholders is essential to building and maintaining legitimacy (Yang & Aldrich, 2017).

In this sense, it is understood that an analysis of the rudimentary creative businesses' liability of newness in the municipality of Grão-Mogol also involves the analysis of the factors that make up this potential for vulnerability. By analyzing internal and external factors, core competences, and legitimacy, it is possible to understand a range of possibilities for public policies that aim to enhance the empowerment of local creative workers.

Methods

This is a qualitative, exploratory and descriptive research. As the main technique, we opted for a qualitative case study, based on a previous theory for the subsequent analysis of the particularities of the case (Abdalla et al., 2018). For data collection, 14 semi-structured interviews were conducted with creative business owners (formalized or informal) in the municipality of Grão-Mogol, Brazil. Defining this sample, the researchers first asked the local government for a list of the city's businesses. Based on this list, a filter was made of the creative economy businesses that met the research criteria, totaling 22. After contacting all of them, 14 of them agreed to be interviewed.

The interviews were transcribed and analyzed with the aid of the Atlas-ti 8 software. Both the script of questions and the codes of analysis were derived from the categories proposed by Stinchcombe (1965) to characterize the Liability of Newness. 34 Analysis codes were generated, which were assigned to 541 citations. Each of these citations was grouped into one or more themes of analysis, generating a matrix of citations to be analyzed in their content (Bardin, 1977), as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Citations by Theme

Elements	Quotes
External Factors	
Difficulty accessing Resources	39
Difficulty in Establishing Bonds	66
Legal Bureaucracy	43
Internal Factors	
Absence of Organizational Routines	41
Learning Need;	32
Management Need;	61
Low legitimacy	
Lack of Social Capital;	71
Lack of Insertion in Networks;	47
Lack of Access to Stakeholders;	42
Core Competences	
Lack of Market Understanding;	68
Lack of Competitive Advantages;	46
Lack of Market Positioning	65

Source: Research data, 2024.

From the analysis of the content, it was possible to establish the analyses and inferences presented in this paper, organizing the data reading by themes, as defined below, based on the data saturation.

Main findings

Most of the interviewees did not have a formal introduction to the profession through formal education. A significant portion of the interviewees started in informality for some *hobby*, family tradition, or experimentation, after seeing a video on the internet or tutorial material on handicrafts, cooking, or some other rudimentary art.

The dimension of family tradition in the offer of value and the competitive differential was perceived in several excerpts of interviews, especially concerning the value proposition offered to the customer (the value of the product derives from the history of the family).

The issue of formalization was identified only in cases where government agencies intervened through formalization campaigns, awareness, and training. Formalization became an obligation only when the entrepreneur began providing their products or services to companies and government organizations.

The main customer groups for the respondents are tourists, schools and companies that promote leisure events for their staff. Many entrepreneurs utilize the registration of previous companies to engage in creative economy activities. The identity of the entrepreneur and his history were reported as the great value differential for the customer. Personalized service and story sharing, including meeting people, talking to them, and taking an interest in their lives, is considered a competitive advantage. Especially in cooking, there is a great emphasis on the

quality of food ingredients (direct from nature) and the final quality of the product offered.

It was also observed that the family plays a strategic role in the social economy. The family is a common source of knowledge necessary for the development of businesses, particularly in the artisanal sector, where it often constitutes the most experienced workforce among the staff of creative economy companies. It is the family group that usually constitutes the business's initial clientele (it is through the dissemination of the family that the business gains traction).

The income composition is mixed: usually, some family members perform other economic activities (formal jobs, liberal professionals), or are retired. The creative business is not the main source of income for a significant portion of the interviewees (they alternate between professions).

External Factors

Regarding the dimension of sources of funds, it was predominantly observed that the interviewees do not have financial management structures and do not have exact control of the volume of inflows and outflows of financial resources from their economic activity. It was reported by several interviewees the desire to structure, expand the business and invest in new equipment and materials, however, the recurrent impediment is in the management of financial resources itself.

On the other hand, some challenges were reported in relation to the creation of bonds within the business environment. If, on the one hand, competitive relations are guided by dynamics of coexistence, given the surplus of demand and the scarcity of supply, on the other hand, it was reported that the capacity for cooperation is still low among entrepreneurs.

Finally, concerning the dimension of legal bureaucracy, it was observed that the respondents had great difficulty in formalizing their businesses. Before the implementation of the "Cordilheira do Espinhaço" Project, the relationship with the local public administration was also reported to be one of sporadic cooperation, lacking a structured public policy to promote local tourism. The only public services mentioned were courses offered by the city hall and by the small business service (SEBRAE).

In summary, it was observed that the business environment presents limitations and challenges to the development of new businesses, especially due to the difficulty of access to credit, social governance and legal bureaucracy. There are opportunities for improvement in relation to the creation of structuring public policies, however, there are limitations derived from the internal environment of creative enterprises, which will be discussed below.

Internal Factors

Regarding the execution of organizational routines, it was noticed from the data that the work is not usually structured and standardized in the field of local creative enterprises. It has been reported that the entrepreneur's experience is the determining factor of production. However, a portion of the respondents reported not dedicating themselves fully to the business, as the profit derived from the creative enterprise would not, by itself, provide an adequate subsistence condition. This is the reason why several entrepreneurs reported having other jobs and economic activities.

Additionally, it was observed that, in addition to non-standardized production procedures, the most structured businesses rely on family support to create routines of service to the public. The family issue also significantly impacts the learning aspect, as the sources of information and knowledge for the profession are often informal. The interviewees reported that the main sources of information are those available on the internet, among friends and, eventually, derived from courses offered by the city hall.

Finally, the management dimension was also characterized as a source of great challenges. Regarding labor, there is a shortage of qualification, and usually entrepreneurs rely on family members to help them in their activities, dividing the profit of the business in a commissioned way. Marketing management, in turn, is also incipient, with social networks such as Instagram and Facebook being the main sales channels. The interviewees reported that one of the biggest sales channels are their own family members, who offer the products to their own.

What can be seen is that, in relation to internal factors, there is a deficit of knowledge in relation to the management and organization of work, which makes it extremely difficult to produce on a scale sufficient to give the business traction to be self-sustainable. The management of the business is usually shared among family members, who are generally involved in all functional areas of the business.

Low Legitimacy

The dimension of social capital was one of the weaknesses reported by the interviewees. Due to the small size of the municipality, there is a shared sense that everyone knows and respects one another. However, difficulties were reported in establishing areas for cooperation, as previously discussed.

It can be seen, from the interviewee's statement, that the notion of trust, value and exchange between social actors happens from a family metaphor. In this sense, each family takes care of its own affairs, without the need for professional integration to enhance the local market, as the municipality would be, itself, a 'big family'.

This rudimentary character of business production creates a contradiction in which there is a good interpersonal relationship between the local inhabitants, but low capacity to convert these relationships into business opportunities. The issue of

the lack of structuring relations with the public authorities in a structured and organized policy to train and empower local creative workers was also mentioned as a major limitation to obtaining governance with suppliers, new customers and accessing new channels for sales.

These elements, when combined, result in a general scenario of difficulty in accessing strategic resources, such as technologies, new equipment, and machinery, so that it is possible to expand the scale of business in the region.

Core Competences

Typically, entrepreneurs rely on improvisation, as they often lack the technical preparation necessary for effective business management, particularly in financial and technological aspects. The learning curve and the growth of the business evolves organically, based on the ties established by the informal path of entrepreneurs, friends, family, customers, and local institutions. It was obtained that one of the aspects that constitutes a competitive advantage of these businesses is the entrepreneur's interpersonal relationship capacity and their *storytelling* ability to build attractive narratives for the consumer. It was reported that the movement of the clientele could also be enhanced by policies that honor festivals and local events, which would bring greater movement of customers to the municipality and customers to local businesses.

However, the formation of the work routine is organic, given that the primary purpose of the business is to maintain a standard of subsistence that meets local desires. The interviewees made it clear, throughout the data collection, that they did not form businesses to develop large fortunes, as this would require a great effort of learning, structuring, dedication, mental load and stress.

The element of quality of life and symbiosis with the environment also appeared in several moments of the interviews, demonstrating that the issue of environmental sustainability, the use and practices of environmental sustainability, are an important characteristic of the lifestyle and production of businesses in the region. This fact, in turn, is particularly relevant in a context where ecotourism is the primary local economic activity. The idea behind creative ventures, in this sense, is to supplement income and develop a good lifestyle based on work for survival, rather than productivity.

According to the analysis of the quotations, concepts such as productivity, competitiveness, and market positioning, among other concepts associated with the idea of traditional economic growth and development, do not apply to the local reality. The concept of development in the case studied appears to be centered on the notion of growing to a point where life is good and peaceful enough.

For some interviewees, accumulating capital was not a primary need. The very idea of scale, productivity, and professionalization would mischaracterize their offer and their identity. It is a perspective that gives rise to a concept of development for a good life, rather than merely meeting market demands. In this sense, there are

significant dissonances between the idealized growth of the business environment and local aspirations.

Discussions & implications

The results found describe a dissonant scenario of the concept of economic development, which is typically established in traditional literature. It is a business environment that does not intend to become a space for accumulation. There's a sense of preservation. Firstly, the findings of the case study contradict previous research regarding the issue of work vulnerability (Comunian & England, 2020; Haubrich et al., 2020); It is, moreover, a relationship of subsistence for the quality of life, and not necessarily for the accumulation of wealth, which relativizes the conditions of production and work. Secondly, this paper confirms issues previously identified in the field of rudimentary creative economy, such as sustainable relations with the environment, the transposition of the artist's identity to his product, and the lack of a structured management by the planning and formal organization of the productive activity (Almeida et al., 2021; Wright, 2018).

What this research adds to the field of creative economy is the social, cultural, economic and political role of family units in the organization of work and production. It was perceived that the family environment constitutes the genesis of business, as well as creating a 'protection and incubation shield' for nascent enterprises.

Regarding the Liability of Newness (LoN) categories, qualitatively analyzed, it was observed that in the Grão-Mogol context, there is a high level of vulnerability for nascent businesses. However, businesses resist and maintain themselves, even if they do not generate profitability. At first, it seems like a contradiction to the theory, but a close analysis of the data allowed us to conclude that many local businesses are not born to be profitable, but rather to supplement income and provide a minimum subsistence for the local inhabitants.

For this reason, this research contributes to the literature by describing and exploring the severe conditions of the economic environment in which creative ventures emerge in countries of the Global South, as well as suggesting key points for public authorities to consider in boosting local creative commercial activity.

Conclusions

This research demonstrates how the Liability of Newness (LoN) of creative businesses imposes the primary barriers to the development of new creative businesses in the case studied. It also found profound and unexpected dimensions in the relationship between culture and economy. If, on the one hand, the application of the LoN model found a scenario conducive to the failure of creative businesses, on the other hand, the cultural and social environment of the place demonstrated that businesses can survive without the need to be profitable, since the moral value behind such ventures are others than accumulation.

Such questions shed light on four key ideas that emerged throughout this research: a) the local cultural phenomenon is complex and can subvert the very notion of creative economy in its traditional sense (culture as a consumer good); b) the creative economy is not necessarily restricted to the traditional idea of accumulation, and can manifest itself in different forms; c) the family nucleus plays a fundamental role in the creation and incubation of nascent enterprises; and d) a notion of economic development emerges limited to providing conditions of good life to the agents, according to their own cultural conceptions about what life project is adequate for themselves.

We suggest that there may be other development economies and organizational configurations that do not follow cosmopolitan logics and are not driven by capital accumulation (Couto et al., 2019). In this sense, capturing other realities can enrich our ideas about the various manifestations of human organizations in different contexts.

As limitations of the case study approach, it focused on a single municipality in Brazil. These include the limited generalizability of the findings, the relatively small sample size of 14 interviewees and the potential influence of the researchers' backgrounds and perspectives on interpreting the research data.

References

Abdalla, M. M., Oliveira, L. G. L., Azevedo, C. E. F., & Gonzalez, R. K. (2018). Quality in qualitative organizational research: Types of triangulation as a methodological alternative. *Administração: ensino e pesquisa*, 19(1).

Agência Minas (2023) Projeto “Cordilheira do Espinhaço” é lançado com proposta de potencialização, estruturação e capacitação. <https://www.secult.mg.gov.br/noticias-artigos/7664-projeto-cordilheira-do-espinhaco-e-lancado-com-proposta-de-potencializacao-estruturacao-e-capacitacao>

Almeida, E. L., Dias, P. K., & Santos, E. C. (2021). Desafios de empreendedoras na economia criativa periférica. *Revista Pensamento Contemporâneo em Administração*, 15(1), 122-146.

Almeida, A. S., & Teixeira, R. M. (2016). A criação de negócios de micro e pequeno porte da economia criativa. *Revista Eletrônica de Ciência Administrativa*, 15(2), 74-89.

Alves, E. P., & Souza, C. A. D. C. (2012). A economia criativa no Brasil: o capitalismo cultural brasileiro contemporâneo. *Latitude*, 6(2), 119-173.

Bardin, L. (1977). *Análise de conteúdo*. Edições 70.

Bolaño, C., Lopes, R., & Santos, V. (2016). Uma economia política da cultura e da criatividade. *Por um Brasil criativo: significados, desafios e perspectivas da economia criativa brasileira* (pp.9-24). BDMG Cultural.

Cavalcante, J. E. R. (2014). Direitos culturais e direitos humanos: uma leitura à luz dos tratados internacionais e da constituição federal. *THEMIS: Revista da Esmeac*, 12, 243-267.

- Comunian, R., & England, L. (2020). Creative and cultural work without filters: Covid-19 and exposed precarity in the creative economy. *Cultural trends*, 29(2), 112-128.
- Costa, R. V. (2008). Cultura e patrimônio cultural na Constituição da República de 1988: a autonomia dos direitos culturais. *Revista CPC*, (6), 21-46.
- Costa, A. J. D., & Souza-Santos, E. R. (2011). Economia criativa no Brasil: quadro atual, desafios e perspectivas. *Economia & Tecnologia (UFPR)*, 27, 151-159.
- Couto, F. F., Honorato, B. E. F., & Silva, E. R. D. (2019). Organizações outras: diálogos entre a teoria da prática e a abordagem decolonial de Dussel. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*, 23, 249-267.
- DeVaughn, M. L., & Leary, M. M. (2018). Learn by doing or learn by failing? The paradoxical effect of public policy in averting the liability of newness. *Group & Organization Management*, 43(6), 871-905.
- Fioravante, A. S. A., & Emmendoerfer, M. L. (2019). Indústrias criativas: reflexões à luz da microeconomia. *Revista Gestão e Desenvolvimento*, 16(2), 170-185.
- Haubrich, G. F., Bessi, V. G., Bohnenberger, M. C., & Freitas, E. C. D. (2020). Reflections on work in the contemporary context of the creative economy. *Organizações & Sociedade*, 27(93), 255-267.
- Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística (2024). *IBGE Cidades e Estados*. <https://www.ibge.gov.br/cidades-e-estados/mg/grao-mogol.html>.
- Leitão, C. (2016). Ter ou não ter o direito à criatividade, eis a questão: sobre os desafios, os impasses e as perspectivas de um Brasil criativo. *Por um Brasil criativo: significados, desafios e perspectiva da economia criativa brasileira* (pp. 309-380). BDMG Cultural.
- Machado, A. F. (2016). Economia da Cultura e Economia Criativa: consensos e dissensos. *Por um Brasil criativo: significados, desafios e perspectivas da economia criativa brasileira*, 1, 53-62.
- Meleiro, A., & Fonseca, F. (2012). Economia Criativa: uma visão global. *Latitude*, 6(2).
- Moraes, I. A. (2018). Economia criativa e desenvolvimento sustentável na América Latina: potencialidades e desafios. *Diálogo com a Economia Criativa*, 3(9), 22-43.
- Pacheco, A. P. D. C., & Benini, E. G. (2018). A Economia Criativa em época de crise: o desenvolvimento endógeno brasileiro na obra de Celso Furtado. *Brazilian Journal of Political Economy*, 38, 324-337.
- Paglioto, B. F. (2016). Economia Criativa: mediação entre cultura e desenvolvimento. *Por um Brasil criativo: significados, desafios e perspectivas da economia criativa brasileira* (pp.25-52). BDMG Cultural.
- Santos, F. P., & Davel, E. (2022). Gestão de organizações culturais: perspectivas, singularidades e paradoxo como horizonte teórico. *Cadernos EBAPE. BR*, 20, 35-49.
- Schlesinger, P. (2019). The creative economy: invention of a global orthodoxy. In *The Structural Change of Knowledge and the Future of the Social Sciences* (pp. 73-90). Routledge.

- Silva, F. A. B., Vieira, M. P., & Franco, B. L. (2019). *A economia criativa sob medida: conceitos e dinamismo das classes criativas* (No. 2493). Texto para Discussão.
- Stinchcombe, A. L. (1965). Organizations and social structure. In P. P. March (Ed.) *Handbook of organizations* (pp.142-193). Rand McNally.
- Suchman, M. C. (1995). Managing legitimacy: Strategic and institutional approaches. *Academy of Management Review*, 20(3), 571-610.
- Wiklund, J., Baker, T., & Shepherd, D. (2010). The age-effect of financial indicators as buffers against the liability of newness. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 25(4), 423-437.
- Winborg, J. (2015). The role of financial bootstrapping in handling the liability of newness in incubator businesses. *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 16(3), 197-206.
- Wright, D. (2018). "Hopeful work" and the creative economy (pp.311-325). *The Palgrave handbook of creativity at work*.
- Yang, T., & Aldrich, H. E. (2017). "The liability of newness" revisited: Theoretical restatement and empirical testing in emergent organizations. *Social Science Research*, 63, 36-53.
- Zhang, W., & White, S. (2016). Overcoming the liability of newness: Entrepreneurial action and the emergence of China's private solar photovoltaic firms. *Research Policy*, 45(3), 604-617.

Creative economy and tourism: Mapping of enterprises and tourist routes in Grão Mogol

*Pablo Peron de Paula
State University of Montes Claros
Brasil*

Introduction

Grão Mogol is a historic city in the north of Minas Gerais that has been emerging as a tourist destination. Its privileged location along Brazil's only mountain range, the Serra do Espinhaço, has established it as a destination with the potential to offer various forms of tourism. With a historical heritage linked to mining, the municipality has reinvented itself over the years through its natural and cultural geography, attracting the attention of visitors and investors to the region. The city stands out for its natural landscapes, such as rock formations, waterfalls, trails, and its cultural heritage, including historic churches and a natural nativity scene. The integration between tourism and the creative economy is fundamental for local development. This link seeks to connect tourist activities with the internal production of goods and services, generating revenue and promoting sustainable economic growth. For this, it is essential to map the creative economy enterprises linked to tourism, handicrafts, and gastronomy. Thus, knowledge of the cultural, natural, and tourist potential of the territory is essential to support the formulation of interconnected local public policies. It is in this context that the present work, based on a mapping of the creative economy enterprises linked to tourism, handicrafts, gastronomy, and built cultural heritage, proposes the creation of tourist routes in Grão Mogol, where these areas are used to diversify its economic activities and promote local development. The interaction between tourism and the creative economy in Grão Mogol creates a synergy that benefits both areas. While tourism brings visitors who may become consumers of creative products and events, these creative initiatives, in turn, enrich the tourism offering, providing more authentic and engaging experiences.

Creative Economy and Tourism

The creative economy is a concept that has different definitions and forms of measurement, being constructed from the different propositions made by scholars and countries that have placed it at the center of their discussions. The term has been applied in the formulation of public policies to highlight economic activities ranging from the most traditional to the most complex technologies, accompanying the globalized debate that is incorporated and adapted to national and local government agendas.

The idea of a creative economy has been consolidating as a set of activities, goods, and services based on creativity. According to Machado (2016), the segment emphasizes small-scale production, whether immaterial or intangible, opening space for different fields in which the distinction from other economic activities

would be given by the incorporation of the symbolic, aesthetic, copyright, and use of technologies.

For Reis (2008, p. 24), “the creative economy comprises sectors and processes that have creativity as an input, especially culture, to generate locally and distribute globally goods and services with symbolic and economic value”. This approach includes the creative industries, understood as a set of specific economic sectors, whose selection is variable depending on the potential economic impact it plays in each region or country.

Tourism, in turn, as a political and economic project for a certain region, must consider in a transversal way the activities present in each locality, in order to integrate the actors. In making this inference, Oliveira, Araujo, and Silva (2013) point out that:

The creative industries can reinforce culture as values and traditions that identify a community or nation. In addition to the role of social cohesion and inclusion, this reinforcement has the potential to generate tourist attractiveness. This is the way in which the creative economy relates to culture and tourism. Another way relates to cultural tourism centered on heritage. The creative economy approach can contribute to the rational and sustainable exploitation of this type of tourism and to the preservation of heritage, the environment, and for the benefit of local populations (Oliveira; Araujo; Silva, 2013, p. 8).

The relationship between tourism and the creative economy lies in the recognition and inclusion of culturally developed practices, services, and activities that can be inserted in this process. According to Emmendoerfer and Ashton (2014):

Tourists travel in search of the consumption of cultural goods for an authentic and meaningful experience, only possible by involving the sociocultural and historical issues that form a certain culture, transforming creative territories into their main space of tourist consumption (Emmendoerfer; Ashton, 2014, p. 467).

Reinforcing the concept, according to Richards (2010), creative tourism allows for greater interaction between the tourist and the visited destination. This involvement results in self-growth, much more than just the material aspect of consumption. According to the Creative Tourism development plan of Recife (2018), in this type of activity, “visitors and hosts get mixed up, exchange and create the experience itself together”.

The first experience of mapping the “creative industries” was carried out in 1998 by the Department of Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS) of Great Britain in the United Kingdom. The production of the “Practical Guide to Mapping the Creative Industries” points out at least seven necessary steps to be taken for the mapping to fulfill its objectives, which include: the purpose of the mapping; the public policies that can be influenced by the mapping; definition of the creative industries; definition of who will do the work; choice of the investigative approach; articulations between the results and the public policy agendas; and how to maintain dynamism (BOP, 2010).

In Brazil, the effort to classify the sectors of the creative economy was elaborated by the Secretariat of Creative Economy, which defined them as all those whose

productive activities have as their main process a creative act that generates symbolic value, a central element in the formation of the price, and which results in the production of cultural and economic wealth (MINC, 2011). From this understanding of the relationship between creative economy and tourism, as well as the need to know the local potential for their promotion, we sought to map the natural and cultural attractions, tourist and creative economy enterprises in the municipality of Grão Mogol.

Methodology

Defining Creative Economy Activities

First, it was necessary to define which activities would be considered as creative economy based on the local reality, a fundamental step for the mapping (BOP, 2010). Thus, for the realization of this work, some institutional documents were used as a reference for the identification of creative economy activities, such as the Referential Framework of Cultural Domains proposed by Unesco (2009) and the System of Information and Cultural Indicators of IBGE (SIIC, 2023).

Handicraft is defined by Brandão, Silva, and Fischer (2012, p. 199) as “a creative process that generates symbolic value and has a strong relationship with the culture, tradition, and identity of the place where it is produced”. Ramos (2013) emphasizes that handicraft is essentially a work made by human hands. In this work, we chose to use the classification given by ordinance no. 1,007-SEI, of June 11, 2018, of the Federal Government, which, in general terms, defines that handicraft must be predominantly manual, express Brazilian cultural identities, transform the raw material, and carry out the complete productive cycle.

Regarding gastronomy, considered within the scope of cultural heritage, it involves local traditions, customs, and tastes passed down between generations (Corner & Angelo, 2008). Ferreira (2017) discusses the Brazilian creative cities (which have the Unesco seal), and brings as main characteristics of gastronomy in the creative economy the existence of traditional local dishes that involve the use of typical local ingredients and seasonings, in addition to fostering local cultural expressions.

The built cultural heritage, according to Ribeiro et al. (2005), is a testimony of the historical moment in which it was built and of human artistic knowledge, that is, it corresponds to a junction between art, technique, and the historical context. The built cultural heritage is marked by its singularity, possessing artistic, architectural, and urbanistic value (Preissler, 2010). Thus, it corresponds to the historical constructions and architectural characteristics of the place.

Location and mapping of creative economy activities

The initial data collection was carried out from institutional contact with the Municipal Secretariat of Tourism of Grão Mogol, which indicated enterprises and experiences linked to tourist and creative economy activities in the municipality. Subsequently, the research team carried out fieldwork to map the previously indicated experiences. The mapping occurred from direct contact with the

enterprises, as well as with local leaders and from the indications made by the actors involved in creative economy activities themselves, thus constituting the use of the snowball technique. To carry out the mapping, the research team conducted fieldwork during two distinct periods: November 20-24, 2023, and December 20-22, 2023. This involved approximately four field visits where the teams, equipped with GPS devices and interview scripts, covered both the urban area and the rural districts of the municipality.

The actors found were presented with the proposal of the project to map the creative economy activities in the region and, with their consent, through the signing of a term, the georeferenced data were collected using the GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System). These data were organized in the QGIS software, a Geographic Information System (GIS).

For the elaboration of all maps, the databases of IBGE (municipal limits), the Prístino Institute (Conservation Units), IDE SISEMA - Spatial Data Infrastructure of the State System of Environment and Water Resources) (hydrography), and the Secretariat of State for Culture and Tourism of Minas Gerais (List of IGR's of 2024) were used.

Elaboration of Tourist Routes

Maia and Baptista (2011, p. 674) address the elaboration of a tourist route according to Paula and Bastos (2002):

It must consist of four stages: defining which route to implement, presenting which tourist attractions will make up the route, carrying out the geographical and access survey that connects the tourist attractions and implementing a program that will trace the route.

Based on this methodology presented by the authors, five stages were carried out for the elaboration of the three tourist routes. In the first, a bibliographic review on tourist routes was carried out. In the second, it was defined which routes would be created from the mapped points. For this, the points were inserted in the uMap platform, a platform that creates maps with OpenStreetMap layers and incorporates them into a website (uMap, n.d.). In this way, it is possible to elaborate non-static maps and make them available on a website, a resource that can be shared among residents, actors involved in the routes, tour guides, the Grão Mogol City Hall website, among others.

In Stage 3, the points to compose the route were selected from the criteria of "geographical proximity", "type", "subtype", "possibility of providing an experience/experience for tourists". In Stage 4, after inserting and selecting the points that would compose the route, the best routes were traced in uMap, aligning distances that can be covered on foot, by car, or by bicycle. Finally, in stage 5, the points and the line that make up each tourist route were downloaded from uMap. In QGIS, the kml file generated in uMap was inserted, along with the files of municipalities and federation units from IBGE (2022), thus finalizing the elaboration of the static maps of each tourist route

Results and Discussion

Mapping of creative economy activities and natural attractions

The fieldwork resulted in the mapping of 26 creative economy activities and/or enterprises. These were categorized into ten handicraft operations, ten gastronomic ventures, and six inventoried cultural attractions. The handicraft productions, which include arts in wood, painting, sewing, crochet, embroidery, and photography, are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Description of Handicraft Enterprises

Handicraft	Description
Artes em Pedra	Handicrafts carved in local stone, church, water fountains, houses, paintings.
Mega Mag Ateliê	Creative sewing, crochet, embroidery, trousseaus.
Ateliê do Artista Plástico	Drawing and painting pictures.
Grão Detalhe	Fabric handicrafts, such as doorstops, placemats, decorative items.
Paulino's Artesanato	Personalized photographs and crafts (mugs, pictures, keychains, utensils, decoration).
Grazeane - Artesanato e Quitandas	Handicrafts made from recyclable materials such as milk cartons and cardboard.
Ateliê da Cida	Creative sewing.
Casinha do Garimpeiro	Cultural space and handicrafts made from recyclable materials.
Mestre dos Carrinhos	Making miniature wooden cars.
Movéis Rústicos	Production of rustic wooden furniture.

Source: authors' elaboration.

In gastronomy, fairs, snack bars, production of liqueur, wines, cottage cheese, cheeses, jams, snacks, and savory pastries were identified and are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Description of Gastronomy Enterprises

Gastronomy	Production
Vinícola Vale do Gongo	Wine production
Gaspar	Cachaça, cheeses, sweets and jellies.
Lúcia	Cheeses.
Neuza	Cottage cheese.
Wagner	Sweets and brown sugar.
Jurandy	Cheeses.
Ponto do Café	Production and sale of quince jam.
Feirinha	Weekly market for the sale of products
Neia Confeitaria	Baked goods.
Elias	Sweets and beijú.

Source: authors' elaboration.

Regarding the built cultural heritage of Grão Mogol, six key sites were identified, including a House of Culture, a notable nativity scene, and four historic churches, as detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Description of Built Cultural Heritage

Built Cultural Heritage	Description
Casa da Cultura	Used as a public library, for cultural events, meetings and other activities.
Presépio Mãos de Deus	Largest open-air nativity scene in the world.
Matriz de Santo Antônio	Historic church built in the second half of the 19th century, listed by the municipality.
Igreja do Rosário	Historic church where the traditional Feast of Our Lady of the Rosary takes place.
Igreja Senhora Sant'ana	Church in the Barrocão district of Grão Mogol, where the Feast of Our Lady of Sant'ana is celebrated.
Igreja do Vau	Church located on the banks of the Itacambiruçu River, in the rural area of the municipality.

Source: authors' elaboration.

The mapping also identified 12 key natural attractions, ranging from trails and waterfalls to a state park, which are fundamental to the region's tourism potential. These attractions are detailed in Table 4.

Table 4: Description of Natural Attractions

Attraction	Description
Trilha da Tropa	Approximately 6 km trail, associated with the history of the drovers.
Trilha Ribeirão do Inferno	Trail that follows paths in the Ribeirão do Inferno region, a watercourse linked to diamond exploration.
Trilha do Vau	3.5 km trail that connects the urban perimeter of Grão Mogol to Praia do Vau.
Trilha do Barão	Historic trail built by slaves, 14 km.
Trilha do Curral de Pedra	Approximately 17 km trail, depicting the period of diamond exploration.
Lapa da Água Fria	The Lapa da Água Fria is located near the Trilha da Tropa, it is a rock cavity with running water inside.
Praia do Val	Freshwater beach.
Barragem de Extrema	Dam where you can enjoy a beautiful sunset.
Cachoeira Vêu das Noivas	Waterfall with a drop of approximately 34 meters.
Cachoeira do Mirante	Waterfall with a drop of approximately seven meters high.
Cachoeira do Balneário	The waterfall is on a private property, Pousada Balneário do Córrego has, in addition to lodging, natural pools, leisure areas, and a restaurant.
Parque Estadual de Grão Mogol	Conservation Unit that preserves the local fauna, flora, and water resources.

Source: authors' elaboration.

Strategic Development of Tourist Routes

Based on the mapping of creative economy enterprises and regional attractions, this study proposes the development of three strategic tourist routes. These routes are designed not as prescriptive itineraries for consumption, but as a framework for developing the local tourism infrastructure. The objective is to structure the supply side by integrating disparate attractions and enterprises into cohesive products that enhance the visitor experience and create value for the local community.

The development of such routes requires a participatory approach, involving local entrepreneurs, community leaders, and public authorities to ensure their consolidation and long-term success. The following proposals, therefore, outline the foundational structure of each route, detailing the key assets to be integrated and the strategic focus intended to shape the local tourism offerings.

Proposals for Tourist Routes in Grão Mogol

The first proposal is the **Sabores de Grão Mogol (Flavors of Grão Mogol) Route**, a 3 km pedestrian circuit designed to integrate the local gastronomy. The development of this route would involve creating a structured pathway that connects key gastronomic points, from small cafes to artisanal producers. The strategic goal is to create a cohesive experience that showcases the region's culinary heritage, encouraging visitors to explore different establishments and products in a planned manner.

Table 5: Points that make up the Flavors of Grão Mogol Tourist Route

Place	Description
Lanchonete da Tina	Known for its delicious delicacies, it is the starting point of the route.
Café Bicalho	Snack bar that also offers a variety of snacks.
Mecesindeira	Offers a combination of snacks and savory treats. Enjoy regional snacks.
Imaculada	Specializing in liqueurs and jams.
Grazeane	Combines crafts and grocery stores. In addition to grocery stores, explore crafts made from recycled materials such as milk cartons and cardboard.
Néia Confeitaria	Offers delicacies and crochet products. Enjoy traditional sweets while admiring local crochet.
Renata	You can enjoy Renata's "sweet dreams".
Léia Delícias Caseiras	Specialist in homemade sweets.
Matriz de Santo Antônio	The final point of the route is an important historic church in the region. End the tour with a visit to the church, admiring its architecture and history.

Source: authors' elaboration.

The Sabores de Grão Mogol Tourist Route focuses on valuing local gastronomy, offering visitors the opportunity to connect with the culture and culinary tradition of

the region. The inclusion of gastronomic enterprises, with an emphasis on snacks, and handicrafts linked through a tourist route, highlights the relationship between the creative economy, cultural identity, and tourism, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Sabores de Grão Mogol Tourist Route

Source: authors' elaboration.

The second proposal, the **Arte e Prosa (Art and Prose) Route**, is a 5.4 km circuit designed to be traveled by car, connecting various artisan workshops and cultural centers. The development of this route would focus on creating opportunities for visitors to engage directly with local artisans, transforming the consumption of handicrafts into an interactive cultural experience. The strategy involves supporting artisans to open their spaces to visitors and structuring the route to tell a story about the region's creative traditions.

Table 6: Points that make up the Arte e Prosa Tourist Route

Place	Description
Grão Detalhe	Starting point of the route, where visitors can learn about the artisans' association and their work.
Mega Mag Ateliê	Atelier specializing in creative sewing, crochet, embroidery and linens. Demonstrations of sewing techniques and creativity in the use of materials.
Paulino's Artesanato	Combining photography and crafts, offering a unique perspective on local culture.
Ateliê da Cida	Focused on sewing, Cida's studio offers an insight into the making of clothing and other fabric items. Sewing techniques and creation of custom pieces.
Artesanato em Pedra	Stone-carved crafts from the region, including representations of churches, water fountains, houses and paintings.
Ateliê do Artista Plástico	Studio dedicated to drawing and painting, offering an insight into the creative process of local visual artists
Mestre dos Carrinhos	Specialized in the manufacture of miniature cars, decorations and wooden utensils. Demonstrations of carpentry skills and creativity in the creation of toys and utensils.
Casa da Cultura	End point of the route, where there is a chat about local history and culture. End of the route with a rich conversation about the local traditions and cultural heritage.

Source: authors' elaboration.

On this route, the visitor can experience an immersion in the local culture and handicrafts. For the artisans, it is an opportunity not only to show their work, but also to tell about their creative process, their inspirations, and meanings, in addition to promoting their products. The Arte & Prosa Tourist Route in Grão Mogol is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Arte e Prosa Tourist Route

Source: authors' elaboration.

The third proposal is the **Caminho das Cachoeiras (Waterfall Path) Route**, a 13 km route accessible by car or bicycle, designed to integrate the region's natural attractions with its cultural and creative offerings. The development of this route would involve improving access and signage to the waterfalls, while also creating linkages with nearby cultural sites, such as the Casinha do Garimpeiro, and local handicraft and gastronomy businesses. The strategy is to offer a diversified experience that combines nature tourism with cultural immersion, thereby broadening the region's appeal.

Table 7: Points that make up the Caminhos das Cachoeiras Tourist Route

Place	Description
Casinha do Garimpeiro	Cultural space that offers crafts made from recyclable materials. Providing visitors with knowledge about the culture and history of local mining.
Artesanato em Pedra	Stone-carved crafts from the region, including representations of churches, water fountains, houses and paintings.
Mecesindeira Quitandas	A place to enjoy traditional local delicacies. Authentic flavors and homemade recipes.
Café Bicalho	Snack bar with various snacks.
Paulino's Artesanato	A place that combines photography and crafts.
Lanchonete da Tina	A place where you can find more traditional snacks. An excellent stop for a typical and tasty snack.
Matriz de Santo Antônio	The region's main church, an important historical and religious landmark, stands out for its architecture.
Grão Detalhe	Association that brings together local artisans and their creations.
Cachoeira do Mirante	First waterfall on the route, ideal for contemplation and a refreshing bath.
Cachoeira do Balneário	The Balneário do Córrego guest house offers day use, where you can enjoy the natural pools and leisure areas.
Cachoeira Veu das Noivas	The final point of the route, one of the most beautiful and impressive waterfalls in the region.

Source: authors' elaboration.

The Caminho das Cachoeiras Tourist Route (Figure 3) offers visitors an immersion in the culture and natural attractions of the region. This route includes cultural, handicraft, and snack enterprises, which are complementary activities and, thus, have the potential for greater attractiveness.

Figure 3: Caminhos da Cachoeira Tourist Route

Source: authors' elaboration.

Conclusion

This study mapped the creative economy activities and tourist attractions in Grão Mogol, revealing a rich landscape of gastronomic and handicraft enterprises rooted in local history and traditions. The analysis of this mapping highlights the municipality's significant tourism potential, based on its natural and cultural assets, and underscores the opportunity for strategic articulation between the creative economy and tourism. The development of integrated tourist routes is presented as a key strategy for diversifying economic activities and promoting sustainable local development.

Despite the identified potential, it is evident that much remains to be done regarding tourism infrastructure, including signage, facility provision, and the formal structuring of routes that connect the region's diverse assets. A participatory approach, involving the entire community, local actors, and public authorities, is essential to harness the economic and social benefits that the creative economy can generate for local development.

To address the incipient stage of tourism consolidation in the region, this paper proposed the creation of strategic tourist routes to interconnect the attractions. The proposal of three distinct routes articulating gastronomy, handicrafts, natural attractions, and cultural heritage demonstrates a viable model for creating tourism products that strengthen and add value to local activities. In this sense, these routes are configured as instruments for fostering co-creation and development with local actors, thereby contributing to economic strengthening and improving the quality of life for the residents of Grão Mogol.

References

- BOP Consulting. (2010). *Guia Prático para o Mapeamento das Indústrias Criativas*. (Série economia criativa e cultura/2). Londres: British Council.
- Brandão, P. M.; Silva, F. R. M.; Fischer, T. (2013). Potencialidades do artesanato no desenvolvimento de destinos turísticos criativos e sustentáveis. *Tourism & Management Studies*, 1, 195-202.
- Circuito Turístico Lago de Irapé: Sobre o circuito (n.d).
<https://www.circuitolagodeirape.com.br/sobre>
- Corner, D. M. R.; Angelo, E. R. B. (2008, junho). O patrimônio cultural imaterial sob a perspectiva da gastronomia. *Anais do V Seminário de Pesquisa em Turismo do MERCOSUL – SeminTUR. Turismo: Inovações da Pesquisa na América Latina*. Caxias do Sul, RS, Brasil.
- Decreto n 43.321, de 08 de maio de 2003. (2003, maio 08). Dispõe sobre o reconhecimento dos circuitos turísticos e dá outras providências.
<https://leisestaduais.com.br/mg/decreto-n-43321-2003-minas-gerais- contem-o-regulamento-do-fundo-de-assistencia-ao-turismo-fastur-criado-pela-lei-n- 11520- de-13-de-julho-de-1994-e-regido-pela-lei-n-15-686-de-20-de-julho-de-2005>.
- Diário Oficial da União. (2018). Portaria nº 1.007-SEI.

- Emmendoerfer, M. L., & Ashton, M. S. G. (2014). Territórios Criativos e suas Relações com o Turismo. *Revista Turismo & Desenvolvimento*, 4(21/22), 459- 468.
- Escobar, A. (2005). O lugar da natureza e a natureza do lugar: globalização ou pós-desenvolvimento?. In E. Lander (Org.). *Título: subtítulo (63-79)*. Buenos Aires: CLACSO, Consejo Latinoamericano de Ciencias Sociales.
- Ferreira, V. M. S. (2017) *A rede de cidades criativas da UNESCO: Uma perspectiva das cidades brasileiras*. Dissertação de Mestrado. Universidade Federal de Goiás, Goiânia, GO, Brasil.
- Franklin, A. Z., Stephan, Í. I. C., & Reis, L. F. (2021). O TURISMO EM PEQUENAS CIDADES DE MINAS GERAIS: CIRCUITOS TURÍSTICOS E ICMS TURÍSTICO. *PIXO-Revista de Arquitetura, Cidade e Contemporaneidade*, 5(19).
- Henriques, F., Gonçalves, A., & Calvo, A. (2010). Caracterização da densidade das lacunas em superfícies pictóricas com recurso a Sistemas de Informação Geográfica (SIG). *Conservar Património*, (11), 3-11.
- IBGE. Malha municipal. Municípios, Brasil. (2020) <https://www.ibge.gov.br/geociencias/organizacao-do-territorio/malhas-territoriais/15774-malhas.html>
- IBGE. Malha municipal. Unidades da Federação, Brasil. (2020) <https://www.ibge.gov.br/geociencias/organizacao-do-territorio/malhas-territoriais/15774-malhas.html>
- IBGE: História Grão Mogol Minas Gerais - MG (n.d). <https://cidades.ibge.gov.br/brasil/mg/grao-mogol/historico>
- IDE Sisema: Infraestrutura de dados espaciais.Massas D'água (ANA/Igam). <https://idesisema.meioambiente.mg.gov.br/webgis>
- Instituto Pristino: Atlas Digital Geoambiental. Unidades de Conservação e Áreas Protegidas (1999). <https://institutopristino.org.br/atlas/>
- Listagem Oficial Retificada IGR's - Publicação em 13 de janeiro de 2024. (2024). Secretaria de Estado de Cultura e Turismo de Minas Gerais. <https://www.secult.mg.gov.br/programas-e-acoas/regionalizacao>
- Lopes, L. M. N. (2016) O rompimento da barragem de Mariana e seus impactos socioambientais. *Sinápse múltipla*, 5 (1), jun 1-14.
- Manzini, E. J. (2003). Considerações sobre a elaboração de roteiro para entrevista semi-estruturada. Marquezine: MC; Almeida, MA; Omote; S. (Orgs.) *Colóquios sobre pesquisa em Educação Especial*. Londrina: eduel, 11-25.
- Marconi, M. D. A., & Lakatos, E. M. (1990). *Técnicas de pesquisa*. São Paulo: Atlas.
- De Oliveira, J. M., de Araujo, B. C. P. O., & Silva, L. V. *Panorama da economia criativa no Brasil*. Rio de Janeiro: Ipea, 2013.

Oliveira, E. P., Machado, B. G., Abreu, L. G. Á. de C. (2015, janeiro - junho). As ecorregiões da reserva da biosfera da serra do espinhaço: elementos para o fortalecimento da conservação da biodiversidade. *Caderno de Geografia*, 25 (43), 18- 33.

Plano do Turismo Criativo de Recife (2018). https://visit.recife.br/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/plano_turismo_criativo.pdf

Preissler, C. (2010). *Identificação de bens edificados considerados patrimônio cultural: o caso do município de Santa Rosa*. Dissertação de Mestrado. Universidade Federal de Santa Maria, RS, Brasil.

Ramos, S. P. (2013). Políticas e Processos Produtivos do Artesanato Brasileiro como Atrativo de um Turismo Cultural. *Rosa dos Ventos*, 5 (1), 44-59.

Ribeiro, R. T. M.; Andrade, I. E.; Coelho, C. M. T.; Melo, C. M. S.; Pimentel, V. L. (2005). Olhares sobre o patrimônio edificado: o conceito de valor. *Anais do XXIII Simpósio Nacional De História*, Londrina, PR, Brasil.

Richards, G. (2010) Trajetórias do desenvolvimento turístico – da cultura a criatividade. *Tourism & Management Studies*, 6, 9-15.

Ruiz, T. C. D., Horodyski, G. S., & Carniatio, I. V. (2019). A economia criativa e o turismo: uma análise do projeto Soucuritiba, de Curitiba-Paraná-Brasil. *Revista Gestão e Desenvolvimento*, 16(2), 145-169.

Secretaria de Estado de Cultura e Turismo de Minas Gerais: Projeto “Cordilheira do Espinhaço” é lançado com proposta de potencialização, estruturação e capacitação. (2003).

<https://www.secult.mg.gov.br/noticias-artigos/7664-projeto-cordilheira-do-espinhaco-e-lancado-com-proposta-de-potencializacao-estruturacao-e-capacitacao>

Secretaria de Estado de Cultura e Turismo de Minas Gerais: Cachoeira Vêu das Noivas. (n.d). <https://www.minasgerais.com.br/pt/atracoes/grao-mogol/cachoeira-veu-das-noivas-0>.

Secretaria de Estado de Cultura e Turismo de Minas Gerais: Cachoeira do Mirante. (n.d). <https://www.minasgerais.com.br/pt/atracoes/grao-mogol/cachoeira-do-mirante>

Sistema de Informações e Indicadores Culturais 2021-2022. Notas técnicas. (2023). Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística, Rio de Janeiro.

Teixeira, M. B. M; Rodrigues, T. M; Resende, I, M. P; Silva, A. J. B; Teodósio, A. S. S. (2020). Crime & Castigo: Narrativas sobre o rompimento da barragem da Vale em Brumadinho. *Revista Brasileira de Estudos Organizacionais*, 7 (3), 18-374-405.

uMap. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://umap.openstreetmap.fr/pt-br/>

Unesco Framework for Cultural Statistics. (2009). Canada, 2009. ISBN 978-92- 9189-075-0.

UNCTAD. Relatório de Economia Criativa. Uma opção de Desenvolvimento (2010): United Nations, Geneva.

Voluntourism Stakeholder Analysis

Markos Psoras
University of the Aegean
Greece

Theodoros Stavrinoudis

Introduction

Voluntourism is the evolution of what started as volunteering trips for humanitarian aid, combining recent years' urge for meaningful vacations by experiencing something different; standing out of the crowd. Voluntourism is a progressively popular form of travel that the research community is not indifferent to (Guttentag, 2009). According to McLennan and Banks (2019, p. 338), "*voluntourism is the phenomenon that fuses the altruistic practice of international volunteering with the hedonistic thrills of the tourism industry, and it has been widely critiqued for commodifying development and reinforcing thin forms of neoliberal global citizenship*". To understand the importance and structure of voluntourism, as well as its global scale, both in the developing and the developed countries, it is essential to identify the major stakeholders. The purpose of this paper is to propose a formalized research approach. By synthesizing the diverse roles identified in the literature into a stakeholder matrix, we provide a tool for analyzing the structural variables and power dynamics that define the industry.

This analysis is in two stages, which are linked. The first stage analyzes the most common stakeholders found in the existing literature and addresses the impact of the stakeholders on the implementation of voluntourism programs as well as the impact of this form of travelling on each stakeholder. Utilizing the findings of the content analysis, the authors develop a stakeholder matrix that categorizes each group according to their roles, responsibilities, and organizational types. The second stage involves a relational analysis, visualized through a stakeholder map. This mapping exercise moves beyond static categorization to illustrate the dynamic interdependencies and power flows between actors. By documenting these connections, the research highlights how the interactions between international intermediaries and local facilitators shape the operational realities of the voluntourism landscape.

The contribution of this analysis lies in identifying the key stakeholder variables that define the global image of voluntourism, thereby providing a structural basis to evaluate emerging trends and suggest future research directions. This approach defines the roles of the stakeholders while it helps the understanding of the connections between stakeholders and the significance of those connections. Findings from the research thus indicate that voluntourism is increasingly being implemented within developed countries (Tsartas et al., 2020; VolunteerWorld, 2023; Vrasti and Montsion, 2014) challenging the dominant view that these activities are mostly implemented in developing countries. Examining these stakeholders explores the complex relationship between voluntourism, development, and social justice. Specifically, it illustrates how the market-driven interests of private agencies (neoliberalization) may overlap or conflict with the civic motivations of volunteers. An other important aspect noteworthy is the integration of UNSDGs on the purpose of the programs (Baillie Smith and Laurie, 2011).

Literature Review

The theoretical foundation of voluntourism was largely established by Wearing (2001), who framed the practice as a pathway for personal development and a de commodified alternative to mass tourism. However, the discourse has since evolved through more critical lenses. Butcher (2003) and Vrsti (2013) argue that voluntourism often functions as a vehicle for neoliberalism, where aid is marketized and the volunteer becomes a consumer of poverty. This is further complicated by what Mostafanezhad (2014) terms the 'sentimental economy' of voluntourism, where the global image of the sector is shaped more by the emotional experiences of the tourist than the material needs of the host.

Voluntourism is particularly prevalent among young adults during the 'Gap Year,' a transitional period typically occurring after secondary education, during university, or upon graduation. During this interval, individuals often pause their formal education to travel or engage in work, seeking practical experience and personal clarity before committing to specific career paths (Simpson, 2004). This experience is frequently included in professional curricula vitae, regardless of its direct relevance to the individual's specific field of study (McGloin and Georgeou, 2015). The proliferation of social media and the increasing desire for experiential travel among youth have significantly contributed to the popularity of these programs. Simultaneously, universities, recognizing the value of international experience and community service, actively support student participation in such initiatives (Hammersley et al., 2018). In some instances, these activities are integrated into formal internships and apprenticeships, frequently supported by institutional funding. Beyond the youth demographic, a distinct category of voluntourists includes retirees from developed nations. The mobilization of this group is often driven by Western governmental policies that seek to reintegrate retirees into the global labor market, utilizing the expertise and 'inactive' human capital of an aging yet economically capable population (Hansen and Slagsvold, 2020).

In addition to the research objectives, this paper highlights specific areas of concern that contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the proposed stakeholder framework. Voluntourism has been on a steady growth course the last decade and has established itself as an innovative form of travel (McLennan, 2014). The relatively recent existence of voluntourism programs in developed countries in addition to developing countries, the emergence of platforms and agencies focusing on this subject is proof that there is fertile ground for further growth (Hammersley et al., 2018). With the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in mind, voluntourism programs promise additionally to being a form of sustainable and alternative tourism, participants to contribute the achievement of the goals set by the United Nations. Popular voluntourism platforms like VolunteerWorld or GoOverseas are openly supporting and integrate these goals into the choices of the facilitators and programs they run (Schech, 2017; Schneller and Coburn, 2018). Each program is usually accompanied by the marking of the goal or goals from the SDGs concerned (Go Overseas, 2023; GoAbroad, 2023; VolunteerWorld, 2023).

Methodology

The methodology employed is qualitative content analysis utilized for the purpose of the stakeholder mapping. By synthesizing existing literature on voluntourism, the authors identify and categorize key stakeholders based on their roles, responsibilities

and influence. This categorization results in a stakeholder analysis matrix, which functions as a conceptual framework for understanding the diverse variables within the sector. Subsequently, the study conducts a deeper analysis of the interdependencies and power dynamics between these actors. This is visualized through a stakeholder relations map, illustrating the flow of resources and influence across the global voluntourism network. Ultimately, this matrix serves as a methodological tool designed to systematize the identification and analysis of variables in future empirical research.

Identifying Voluntourism Stakeholders

In order to systematize our understanding of voluntourism and its implementation, it is necessary to identify the stakeholders involved and the relationships that define their interactions. The primary stakeholders identified across contemporary literature include voluntourists, local communities, facilitators, voluntourism agencies, voluntourism platforms, and local businesses. Additionally, while less frequently discussed, mass tourism businesses represent a structurally significant stakeholder of the sector (McLennan, 2019; Schneller and Coburn, 2018).

The following sections categorize these stakeholders by synthesizing their roles and responsibilities into a structured matrix. This categorization highlights the spectrum of actors through which voluntourism is produced and consumed. By mapping these roles, the analysis transitions from a descriptive list to a relational framework, emphasizing how the interdependencies between local and international actors drive the global voluntourism landscape

Volunteer Tourists or Voluntourists

The primary stakeholders to analyze are the voluntourists. Within the existing literature voluntourist is the standard term for these participants, and it will be utilized through this paper. While early research often focused on altruism (Wearing, 2001), contemporary studies highlight a core demographic originating from the Global North, predominantly from North America, Europe and Australia (Hernandez-Maskivker et al., 2018). The age of participants typically ranges between 18 and 45 years with the average age being 26, though participation among retirees is also documented (Hansen and Slagsvold, 2020).

Voluntourists generally self-fund their experience, covering airfare and travel insurance while paying fees to the facilitating organization for accommodation, airport transfer to the accommodation, administration, support and orientation (Jakubiak, 2020; Lyons, 2003). Participants are usually expected to provide labor three to six hours per day, five days per week, leaving substantial time to socialize, engage within the local community and participate in traditional tourist activities (Broad, 2003). Consequently, voluntourists function as both service providers and consumers. Personal growth remains a primary motive for participation, as individuals seek to develop their personal identities and global perspectives (Schech, 2017).

Literature further distinguishes voluntourists on their primary focus: the "volunteer-minded" and the "vacation-minded" (Coghlan and Gooch, 2011). "Volunteer-minded" individuals prioritize the mission and labor aspects of the trip, whereas "vacation-minded" participants emphasize leisure, socialization, and touristic attractions dedicating a smaller portion of their time to volunteering (Coren and Gray, 2012). This

distinction is central to understanding the varying impacts these actors have to communities.

Facilitators

Responsibility for the implementation of voluntourism programs on a local level rests with entities that typically hold the status of an NGO (van Zyl et al., 2015). Through the stakeholder analysis process, it was observed that this key stakeholder can take various forms. To provide conceptual clarity this paper introduces the term "Facilitator". This designation is intended to assist future research as existing literature often uses inconsistent terminology such as "operators" or "local partners" making it challenging to establish links between relevant studies.

It is vital to understand the role facilitators play in managing various factors required for successful program implementation. They are tasked to maintaining a balance that mutually benefits both the host community and the voluntourists (Hamzah, 2014). In current literature the distinction between Facilitators, Voluntourism Agencies and Voluntourism Platforms is frequently overlooked (Schech, 2017).

Facilitators are responsible for identifying the needs of the host community, securing appropriate placements, and managing logistics such as accommodation and recreational activities (van Zyl et al., 2015). To recruit participants, they utilize websites and social media to promote the uniqueness of the experience, often validating their programs through testimonials and visual media (van Zyl et al., 2015). Furthermore, Facilitators ensure that voluntourists contribute effectively to their placements while adhering to the cultural norms of the host community (Devereux, 2008). Part of their mandate includes preparing the host community for the arrival of voluntourists. It is common for Facilitators to provide recruited voluntourists with orientation sessions to ensure a safe and smooth coexistence (Hammersley, 2013; McMorran, 2017).

Voluntourism Agencies

As the demand for experiential travel grew exponentially, new actors emerged within the voluntourism sector. These entities, frequently identified in the literature as "sending organizations" or "parent organizations" function as Voluntourism Agencies (McLennan, 2019; Schech, 2017).

In some instances, local Facilitators that achieved operational resilience and scale, have undergone vertical integration, transitioning into the role of a voluntourism agency (Lupoli et al., 2015). The operational framework of these organizations closely mirrors that of traditional travel; consequently, conventional tourist agencies have also begun establishing partnerships with local facilitators aiming to get involved in this alternative form of tourism (McLennan, 2014).

To increase their visibility to potential participants, local facilitators often establish cooperations with these agencies. Voluntourism agencies specialize in market promotion, participant recruitment, and the strategic acquisition of new local partnerships to broaden their service portfolios (Hammersley, 2013). It is common for agencies to select an exclusive partner within a specific geographical region and conduct an on-site quality assessment before officially adding a program to their list of offerings. At this point it is worth mentioning that these agencies often prioritize sales

metrics and participant satisfaction over the actual socio-economic impact on the local community or the facilitators capacity to manage volunteer influxes (Schneider, 2018).

Beyond marketing, a key responsibility of these agencies, is the management of the online footprint which involves the curated display of testimonials and the mitigation of negative feedback. While voluntourists often pay significant fees for travel arrangements, insurance and administrative support, the local facilitators usually receive only a percentage of these total costs. (McLennan, 2019).

Voluntourism Platforms

The digital landscape has fundamentally altered how individuals identify and access meaningful travel opportunities, with social media and specialized web aggregators serving as primary search tools (van Zyl et al., 2015). Voluntourism Platforms have emerged as a distinct stakeholder group, functioning as digital marketplaces rather than traditional sending agencies. Prominent examples include “VolunteerWorld” and “Go Overseas”, which were often founded by former voluntourists to address the need for centralized databases that allow users to compare diverse global programs (Go Overseas, 2023; VolunteerWorld, 2023). On these platforms facilitators can upload their available programs accompanied by attractive descriptions and photos containing snapshots of community work and local landscapes to attract potential participants (van Zyl et al., 2015). Unlike Agencies, which often handle full travel logistics, Platforms primarily provide the infrastructure for transparency and comparison.

To maintain institutional credibility, these platforms implement quality assurance protocols based on legal frameworks and internal standards. Evaluation is typically conducted through on-site inspection or the verification of a Facilitator’s organizational documentation. A defining feature of these platforms is the integration of user-generated content, specifically peer-to-peer ratings and testimonials. Voluntourists who have completed a placement can provide verified reviews, which serve as a powerful marketing tool (Go Overseas, 2023; GoAbroad, 2023; VolunteerWorld, 2023). Both Agencies and Platforms leverage these testimonials to foster expectations of a “unique and guilt-free experience,” a narrative that is central to the modern voluntourism market (van Zyl et al., 2015).

Local Community

The local community is the most significant, yet often most vulnerable, stakeholder in voluntourism. Traditionally, research has focused on host communities within the developing world. This landscape has evolved. As the need for environmental, social or humanitarian support exists globally, voluntourism programs are increasingly implemented in developed nations, such as Greece and Italy (Messmore and Davis, 2020; Tsartas et al., 2020). This shift highlights that host communities are defined by a specific localized need rather than a country’s economic status (Omoto et al., 2012).

A community qualifies as a voluntourism destination when there is a clear requirement for support that complements, rather than substitutes for local labor (Jakubiak, 2016). Many of these communities are initially non-touristic as participants in such programs often seek authentic cultural experiences that have not been altered by mass tourism. For a partnership to succeed, there must be mutual respect and clear communication between the community and the facilitator (Messmore and Davis, 2020).

The participation of a local community in such programs can serve as a catalyst for broader development (Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014). In some instances, the presence of voluntourism allows locals to organize resources and utilize their cultural heritage to transition into a more established tourist destination (Hamzah, 2014). However, achieving a sustainable balance requires proper information and engagement of the local community, particularly the institutions that host voluntourists, as well as clear and accurate information for interested potential voluntourists, accompanied by appropriate training and orientation prior to the start of their program.

Local Businesses

Local businesses' reaction towards voluntourists differ depending the region, country and local culture (Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014). At this point it is pertinent to stress that research on the coexistence of voluntourists and local businesses is scarce. There are cases where local businesses benefited from voluntourism and cases where they have treated voluntourists as an obstacle (Hamzah, 2014).

As voluntourism programs are typically found in areas where some form of crisis or need exists (humanitarian, environmental, economic, etc.), the proper handling of voluntourists by local businesses can be a factor of development or moderation of the problem (Hammersley et al., 2018). There have been cases where the majority of local businessmen are against voluntourism, as found in the literature, in communities where there have been particularly sensitive issues such as a refugee crisis (Tsartas et al., 2020). In other cases, the local community embraced voluntourists with examples of locals benefiting of voluntourism and operate commercially aligned with these programs (Aquino and Andereck, 2018). There are also instances in which voluntourists, by promoting their experiences on social media, have contributed to positioning these locations as tourist destinations (Hernandez-Maskivker et al., 2018).

Mass Tourism Businesses

While mass tourism businesses are often peripheral to the volunteer mission, they are identified in the literature as structurally significant stakeholders that ensure the sector's resilience by providing the transport and hospitality infrastructure required for international travel (Guttentag, 2009). As voluntourism destinations mature, these businesses become 'collateral stakeholders' that facilitate the scaling of programs through established logistical networks (Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014).

The inclusion of these actors in the Stakeholder Analysis Matrix (Table 1) highlights the "tourism" dimension of the voluntourism product. For example, the cooperation between facilitators and local tourism businesses to develop "free-time packages" for participants confirms that the experience is marketed and consumed as a leisure-labor hybrid. By documenting these connections, this research provides a structural framework that characterizes voluntourism as an alternative tourism product, rather than a purely humanitarian endeavor. This perspective aligns with critical literature (Butcher, 2003; Vrasti, 2013) that views the sector through the lens of marketized development.

The following Voluntourism Stakeholder Analysis Matrix (Table 1) synthesizes the findings from the content analysis. The stakeholders are categorized by their specific roles, responsibilities, and organizational types, as identified within the literature. This matrix serves as the structural foundation for the subsequent relational mapping,

allowing for a systematic comparison of how international and local stakeholders interact within the voluntourism supply chain.

Table 1: Voluntourism Stakeholder Analysis Matrix

Identification				
Stakeholder	Role	Responsibilities	Type	References
Voluntourism Agencies	Voluntourists suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Find facilitators for cooperation -Financial and sustainability background check of cooperating facilitator - History and impact check of cooperating facilitators - Check cooperating facilitators to meet the Agency's operational standards - Check cooperating facilitator's programs - Check cooperating facilitator's local community impact - Set rules, activity agreement, code of conduct and Terms and Conditions for all cooperations with cooperating facilitator - Publish available programs - Retrieve voluntourists - Receive payments from voluntourists - Responsible for the payment of the local facilitator - May arrange travel insurance - May organize plane tickets - Organize voluntourism programs (more than one destination, VIP packages etc.) 	International Organization	Baillie Smith and Laurie, 2011; Devereux, 2008; Griffiths, 2016; Hammersley, 2013; Lupoli et al., 2015; McLennan, 2014, 2019; Schech, 2017; Schneider, 2018
Voluntourism Platforms	Voluntourists suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperating facilitators' background check and quality control - Set rules for facilitators to register - Set rules for voluntourists to register - Set communication rules between voluntourists and facilitators - Receive commission by volunteers or/and by facilitators - Use a review promotion system for volunteer programs and/or organizations 	International Organization	Aquino and Andereck, 2018; Go Overseas, 2023; GoAbroad, 2023; Sujarittanonta, 2014; van Zyl et al., 2015; VolunteerWorld, 2023

<p style="text-align: center;">Facilitators</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Voluntourism Implementation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responsible for volunteer programs - Running the volunteer programs - Register to platforms and Voluntourism Agencies to recruit voluntourists - Find hosting place for voluntourists - Onsite Support for voluntourists - Responsible to orientate the voluntourists - Create/find volunteer programs - Introduce international voluntourists to the local community - Receive payments from voluntourists or platforms or agencies - Measure the impact of the activities to the local community and the voluntourists 	<p style="text-align: center;">Local Organization</p> <p>Butcher, 2003; Devereux, 2008; Hammersley, 2013; Hamzah, 2014; Hernandez-Maskivker et al., 2018; Jakubiak, 2020; McMorrان, 2017; Mostafanezhad, 2014; Rozakou, 2012; Schech, 2017; Tsartas et al., 2020; van Zyl et al., 2015; Vrasti, 2013; Wearing, 2001</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Voluntourists</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Customers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responsible to carry out the pre-assigned activities - Represent themselves, their country and the hosting organization in the local community - Responsible for the payment of the program they have selected - Write a review or testimony on the online volunteering platforms after finishing their program 	<p style="text-align: center;">International Individuals</p> <p>Bright Founder, 2015; Broad, 2003; Butcher, 2003; Cousins and Sadler, 2009; Devereux, 2008; Doidge et al., 2020; Germann Molz, 2016; Griffiths, 2016; Guiney, 2018; Hammersley, 2013; Hansen and Slagsvold, 2020; Jakubiak, 2020, 2012; Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014; Lyons, 2003; McLennan, 2014; McMorrان, 2017; Millerman, 2016; Mostafanezhad, 2014; Schneider, 2018; Vrasti, 2013; Wearing, 2001</p>

Local Community	Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Respect the other cultures - Recognition of the need for voluntourists - Coordination between voluntourists and locals - Accept international voluntourists to blend with the local community 	Local individuals	<p>Aquino and Andereck, 2018; Baines and Hardill, 2008; Broad, 2003; Butcher, 2003; Coghlan and Gooch, 2011; Coren and Gray, 2012; Hammersley et al., 2018; Hamzah, 2014; Heu, n.d.; Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014; Levinson, 2020; Lupoli et al., 2015; Madziva and Chinouya, 2016; Mostafanezhad, 2014; Palacios, 2010; Spalding, 2013; Vrasti, 2013; Wearing, 2001</p>
Local businesses	Collateral Interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Respect the other cultures - Recognition of the need for voluntourists - Coordination between voluntourists and locals - Treat international voluntourists with respect - Introduce the international voluntourists to the local community 	Local businesses	<p>McLennan, 2019; Messmore and Davis, 2020; Omoto et al., 2012; Woosnam and Lee, 2011</p>
Mass Tourism businesses	Collateral Interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Respect the other cultures - Recognition of the need for voluntourists - Coordination between voluntourists and locals - Treat international voluntourists with respect - Introduce the international voluntourists to the local community - Cooperation with facilitators for the developing of free time packages for international voluntourists 	Local tourism businesses	<p>(Guttentag, 2009; Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014; McLennan, 2019)</p>

Stakeholders Relations Analysis Mapping

In the existing literature, authors argue about the good practices of voluntourism and its impact on local level (Guttentag, 2009; Kinsbergen et al., 2021). Nevertheless, it is empirically evident in various cases that such programs have positive impact on local communities and voluntourists (Hernandez-Maskivker et al., 2018). Cooperation between stakeholders is inextricably linked to the impact and the results of such programs.

The initial gap for the existence of a voluntourism program in a region is first identified by a local team (local group, NGO, CSO, individuals, etc.) (Hamzah, 2014). Following, the local team, having identified the priorities of the action area, assumes the role of the Facilitator. This stakeholder has the responsibility for the implementation, evaluation and dissemination of the results (Devereux, 2008). To attract voluntourists the facilitator must advertise available programs primarily through social media. Another important role of the facilitator is the sufficient training and briefing of both voluntourists and the local community about all the aspects of the programs before implementation. At the same time, facilitators have the role of the intermediary for the resolution of occurring issues that may arise in order to sustain the smooth coexistence of all actors (van Zyl et al., 2015).

From the side of a local community, although receiving aid might initially seem appealing, when it comes to the implementation of the programs the locals' reaction is mixed or skeptical (Baines and Hardill, 2008). Evidently, the effective assistance of the local community by voluntourists is a prerequisite for the existence of these programs. Moreover, there are cases where the activity from voluntourism became the trigger for development in areas of need where local residents capitalized on the arrival of voluntourists (McLennan, 2019). The main stakeholders that should be accounted for the smooth implementation of such a program are the facilitators (Kontogeorgopoulos, 2014).

Local businesses in areas where voluntourism programs exist, usually benefit from the participants in such activities, as the behavior of voluntourists outside of voluntary work is similar to that of a responsible tourist (Messmore and Davis, 2020). On the contrary this is not always the case with mass tourism businesses (Broad, 2003). For instance, since accommodation is typically provided by the facilitator, collaboration with mass tourism businesses such as hotels and restaurants is less frequent.

Facilitators' ability to reach out to individuals interested in voluntourism is limited and this is where the Voluntourism Agencies intervene. The agencies will find facilitators or vice versa, where they already run or are able to run programs and they are assured consistent volunteer flows (Baillie Smith and Laurie, 2011). Agencies are likely to take on some of the facilitators' responsibilities such as the communication and preparation of voluntourists before departure.

In addition, Voluntourism Platforms, despite having only recently emerged as stakeholders, enable facilitators to create a personal account on their platform and post their available programs along with their description. At the same time the platforms can also be used by agencies to promote their programs. These platforms give voluntourists the ability to compare programs and choose the best match for them (Sujarittanonta, 2014).

From the existing literature it appears that as more international stakeholders are involved “controlling” the facilitators (voluntourism agencies, voluntourism platforms), local stakeholders (facilitators, local community, local businesses, mass tourism businesses) become more affected and marginalized (Coren and Gray, 2012). On “Figure 1” is presented the Voluntourism stakeholders Relations Analysis Map. Local stakeholders are represented with green color while international with blue. Voluntourists, since they are on site and their presence is temporary while at the same time their actions influence the locals, are represented with grey.

Figure 1: Voluntourism Stakeholder Map

Scientific Contribution

The scientific contribution of this paper lies in the systematic categorization of key stakeholders providing a structural framework to better understand the global voluntourism landscape. By synthesizing diverse roles into a unified stakeholder analysis matrix, this research identifies the core variables that define the field, offering a foundation for future empirical studies.

Furthermore, this analysis documents the interdependent relationships between local and international actors, visualizing these flows of influence through a stakeholder relations map. By introducing the term “Facilitator”, the paper offers conceptual clarity to an area of the literature often characterized by inconsistent terminology. Ultimately, this research serves as a methodological approach to help scholars examine how voluntourism functions as a development tool or as a crisis response mechanism across both developing and developed nations.

Conclusion

In the existing literature stakeholders in voluntourism are frequently identified in a fragmented manner, with researchers often focusing on specific actors rather than a collective ecosystem. This research provides a systematic foundation by synthesizing previous documentation to offer the academic community a comprehensive record of key stakeholders. The introduction of the term "Facilitator" represents a crucial contribution, as it acknowledges a vital stakeholder that assumes various forms and has previously been difficult to isolate in the literature. Furthermore, by analyzing stakeholder relations through visual mapping, this study provides a clear reference point for future research into the complex forces and interdependencies within the sector.

A significant observation of this paper is that while the majority of the existing research approaches voluntourism from a humanitarian-social perspective, this study, by mapping the systematic involvement of commercial intermediaries, structurally verifies that voluntourism operates as an alternative tourism product within the global market. The resulting matrix clarifies the synergies, cooperations, and interdependencies that exist between actors, highlighting that each stakeholder occupies a specific position in voluntourism with defined, albeit often informal, limits.

By distinguishing frequently conflated roles such as "Voluntourism Agencies", "Voluntourism Platforms" and "Facilitators", this paper provides the conceptual clarity necessary for more rigorous sectoral analysis. While information on newer stakeholders such as "Voluntourism Platforms" remains limited due to their recent emergence, their growing footprint is evident. Ultimately, this research addresses the lack of integrated data on stakeholder roles, providing a framework that can be parameterized across varying scopes of voluntourism globally.

Research Limitations

During the research it was observed that there are several potential gaps that require further analysis in the existing literature of voluntourism. Information about some stakeholders is limited and, in some cases, their online presence was used to explore their roles.

Another issue presented, which stems from the fact that so far research on voluntourism is done from a humanitarian-sociological point of view, is that literature is limited concerning voluntourism programs hosted in the Global North. Whilst, with a simple search in the existing available Voluntourism Platforms and Voluntourism Agencies we can find a plethora of programs in European countries, Australia, etc.

Future Research

Further empirical investigation should be directed toward stakeholders for whom data remains scarce in the current literature, as well as the evolving geography of the sector as developed nations increasingly become destinations for voluntourism action. There is also significant scope for introspective analysis regarding pricing structures and the distribution of fees within voluntourism programs. One frequently documented area of malpractice is the misrepresentation of programs by agencies or facilitators, alongside substandard orientation sessions that fail to prepare participants effectively (Guttentag, 2009). Future studies should also examine the mechanisms through which local

communities and businesses are informed and engaged. As implementation strategies appear to vary based on the facilitator's management choices and the sensitivity of the project, current conclusions remain largely hypothetical. Consequently, the methodological framework provided in this research can serve as a basis for follow-up studies concerning specific branches of voluntourism. This includes further analysis of the power dynamics between stakeholders and the development of best practices for program implementation. Finally, a critical gap remains in the literature regarding the long-term perceptions and reactions of host communities toward these interventions.

References

- Aquino, J.F., Andereck, K., 2018. Volunteer tourists' perceptions of their impacts on marginalized communities. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 26, 1967–1983. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2018.1526295>
- Baillie Smith, M., Laurie, N., 2011. International Volunteering and Development: Global Citizenship and Neoliberal Professionalisation Today. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers* 36, 545–559. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-5661.2011.00436.x>
- Baines, S., Hardill, I., 2008. 'At Least I Can Do Something': The Work of Volunteering in a Community Beset by Worklessness. *Social Policy and Society* 7. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1474746408004284>
- Bright Founder, M., Help From Home, 2015. Microvolunteering for Big Impact, in: *Volunteer ENGAGEMENT 2.0: Ideas and Insights Changing the World*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, pp. 153–168. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119154792.ch12>
- Broad, S., 2003. Living the Thai Life—A Case Study of Volunteer Tourism at the Gibbon Rehabilitation Project, Thailand. *Tourism Recreation Research* 28, 63–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2003.11081418>
- Butcher, J., 2003. *The Moralisation of Tourism*, 0 ed. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203987025>
- Coghlan, A., Gooch, M., 2011. Applying a transformative learning framework to volunteer tourism. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 19, 713–728. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2010.542246>
- Coren, N., Gray, T., 2012. Commodification of Volunteer Tourism: A Comparative Study of Volunteer Tourists in Vietnam and in Thailand. *International Journal of Tourism Research* 14, 222–234. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jtr.848>
- Cousins, J., Sadler, J., 2009. Selling Conservation? Scientific Legitimacy and the Commodification of Conservation Tourism. *ECOLOGY AND SOCIETY* 14.
- Devereux, P., 2008. International volunteering for development and sustainability: outdated paternalism or a radical response to globalisation? *Development in Practice* 18, 357–370. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09614520802030409>
- Doidge, M., Keech, M., Sandri, E., 2020. 'Active integration': sport clubs taking an active role in the integration of refugees. *International Journal of Sport Policy and Politics* 12, 305–319. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19406940.2020.1717580>

- Germann Molz, J., 2016. Making a difference together: discourses of transformation in family voluntourism. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 24, 805–823. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2015.1088862>
- Gharib, M., 2021. The Pandemic Changed The World Of “Voluntourism.” Some Folks Like The New Way Better. NPR.
- Go Overseas, 2023. Go Overseas [WWW Document]. Go Overseas. URL <https://www.gooverseas.com/about/profiles> (accessed 4.28.23).
- GoAbroad, 2023. GoAbroad [WWW Document]. GoAbroad.com. URL <https://www.goabroad.com/about> (accessed 4.28.23).
- Griffiths, M., 2016. Writing the body, writing Others: A story of transcendence and potential in volunteering for development. *The Geographical Journal* 184. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12200>
- Guiney, T., 2018. “Hug-an-orphan vacations”: “Love” and emotion in orphanage tourism. *The Geographical Journal* 184, 125–137. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12218>
- Guttentag, D.A., 2009. The possible negative impacts of volunteer tourism. *International Journal of Tourism Research* 11, 537–551. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jtr.727>
- Hammersley, L., 2013. Volunteer tourism: Building effective relationships of understanding. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 22, 855–873. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2013.839691>
- Hammersley, L., Lloyd, K., Bilous, R., 2018. Rethinking the expert: Co-creating curriculum to support international work-integrated learning with community development organisations. *Asia Pacific Viewpoint* 59, 201–211. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apv.12190>
- Hamzah, A., 2014. Critical Success Factors for Creating Community-Based Tourism, in: *The Wiley Blackwell Companion to Tourism*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, pp. 589–599. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118474648.ch47>
- Hansen, T., Slagsvold, B., 2020. An “Army of Volunteers”? Engagement, Motivation, and Barriers to Volunteering among the Baby Boomers. *Journal of Gerontological Social Work* 63, 335–353. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01634372.2020.1758269>
- Hernandez-Maskivker, G., Lapointe, D., Aquino, R., 2018. The impact of volunteer tourism on local communities: A managerial perspective. *International Journal of Tourism Research* 20, 650–659. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jtr.2213>
- Heu, M., n.d. Challenges of Volunteerism within a Cultural Community: Case Study of Young Hmong Adults in Kitchener-Waterloo.
- Jakubiak, C., 2020. “English Is Out There—You Have to Get with the Program”: Linguistic Instrumentalism, Global Citizenship Education, and English-Language Voluntourism. *Anthropology & Education Quarterly* 51, 212–232. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aeq.12332>
- Jakubiak, C., 2016. Ambiguous Aims: English-language Voluntourism as Development. *Journal of Language, Identity & Education* 15, 245–258. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15348458.2016.1195270>

- Jakubiak, C., 2012. "English for the global": discourses in/of English-language voluntourism. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education* 25, 435–451. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2012.673029>
- Kinsbergen, S., Konijn, E., Kuijpers-Heezemans, S., op 't Hoog, G., Koch, D.-J., Molthof, M., 2021. Informalisation of international volunteering: A new analytical framework explaining differential impacts of the 'orphanage tourism' debate in the Netherlands. *Journal of International Development* 33, 1304–1320. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jid.3577>
- Kontogeorgopoulos, N., 2014. The relationship between volunteer tourism and development in Thailand. *Tourism - An International Interdisciplinary Journal* 62, 239–255.
- Levinson, B.A., 2020. Commentary. *Anthropology & Education Quarterly* 51, 253–256. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aeq.12336>
- Lupoli, C.A., Morse, W.C., Bailey, C., Schelhas, J., 2015. Indicator development methodology for volunteer tourism in host communities: creating a low-cost, locally applicable, rapid assessment tool. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 23, 726–747. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2015.1008498>
- Lyons, K.D., 2003. Ambiguities in Volunteer Tourism: A Case Study of Australians Participating in a J-1 Visitor Exchange Programme. *Tourism Recreation Research* 28, 5–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2003.11081412>
- Madziva, C., Chinouya, M., 2016. 'This word volunteer is killing us: Making sense of volunteering in social welfare provision for orphans and vulnerable children in rural Zimbabwe. *International Social Work* 60. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020872816672518>
- McGloin, C., Georgeou, N., 2015. 'Looks good on your CV': The sociology of voluntourism recruitment in higher education. *Journal of Sociology* 52, 403.
- McLennan, S., 2014. Networks for Development: Volunteer Tourism, Information and Communications Technology, and the Paradoxes of Alternative Development. *PoLAR: Political and Legal Anthropology Review* .37, 48–68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/plar.12050>
- McLennan, S., Banks, G., 2019. Reversing the lens: Why corporate social responsibility is not community development. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management* 26, 117–126. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1664>
- McLennan, S.J., 2019. Global encounters: Voluntourism, development and global citizenship in Fiji. *The Geographical Journal* 185, 338–351. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geoj.12318>
- McMorran, C., 2017. From volunteers to voluntours: shifting priorities in post-disaster Japan. *Japan Forum* 29, 558–582. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09555803.2017.1307257>
- Messmore, N., Davis, J.M., 2020. A Critical Examination of Community Engagement as a Practice to Foster Leadership. *New Directions for Student Leadership* 2020, 63–73. <https://doi.org/10.1002/yd.20409>
- Millerman, M., 2016. Hani A. Faris, ed., (2013). *The Failure of the Two-State Solution: The Prospects of One State in the Israel-Palestine Conflict*. London: I.B. Taurus. 336pp. £58.50 (hbk). *Nations and Nationalism* 22, 392–394. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nana.12173>

- Mostafanezhad, M., 2014. Volunteer Tourism: Popular Humanitarianism in Neoliberal Times. Routledge, London. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315547886>
- Omoto, A.M., Snyder, M., Hackett, J.D., 2012. Everyday Helping and Responses to Crises, in: Restoring Civil Societies. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, pp. 98–118. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118347683.ch6>
- Palacios, C.M., 2010. Volunteer tourism, development and education in a postcolonial world: conceiving global connections beyond aid. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 18, 861.
- Rozakou, K., 2012. The biopolitics of hospitality in Greece: Humanitarianism and the management of refugees. *American Ethnologist* 39, 562–577. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1548-1425.2012.01381.x>
- Schech, S., 2017. International volunteering in a changing aidland. *Geography Compass* 11, e12351. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gec3.12351>
- Schneider, M.J., 2018. Exotic Place, White Space: Racialized Volunteer Spaces in Honduras. *Sociological Forum* 33, 690–711. <https://doi.org/10.1111/socf.12439>
- Schneller, A.J., Coburn, S., 2018. For-profit environmental voluntourism in Costa Rica: teen volunteer, host community, and environmental outcomes. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 26, 832–851. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2017.1421200>
- Simpson, K., 2004. 'Doing development': the gap year, volunteer-tourists and a popular practice of development. *Journal of International Development* 16, 681–692. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jid.1120>
- Spalding, R., 2013. "Daring to Volunteer": some reflections on geographers, geography students and evolving institutional support for community engagement in higher education. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education* 37, 59–64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03098265.2012.757300>
- Sujarittanonta, L., 2014. Voluntourism product development and wildlife conservation for Thailand. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes* 6. <https://doi.org/10.1108/WHATT-10-2013-0040>
- Tsartas, P., Kyriakaki, A., Stavrinoudis, T., Despotaki, G., Doumi, M., Sarantakou, E., Tsilimpokos, K., 2020. Refugees and tourism: a case study from the islands of Chios and Lesbos, Greece. *Current Issues in Tourism* 23, 1311–1327. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2019.1632275>
- van Zyl, I., Inversini, A., Rega, I., 2015. The representation of voluntourism in search engines: The case of South Africa. *Development Southern Africa* 32, 333–349. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0376835X.2015.1010714>
- VolunteerWorld, 2023. VolunteerWorld [WWW Document]. Volunteer World. URL <https://www.volunteerworld.com/static-pages/history> (accessed 4.28.23).
- Vrasti, W., 2013. Volunteer Tourism in the Global South: Giving Back in Neoliberal Times. *Volunteer Tourism in the Global South: Giving Back in Neoliberal Times* 1–166. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203104453>

Vrasti, W., Montsion, J.M., 2014. No Good Deed Goes Unrewarded: The Values/Virtues of Transnational Volunteerism in Neoliberal Capital. *Global Society* 28, 336–355. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600826.2014.900738>

Wearing, S., 2001. *Volunteer tourism: experiences that make a difference*. CABI Publishing, Wallingford.

Woosnam, K.M., Lee, Y.J., 2011. Applying social distance to voluntourism research. *Annals of Tourism Research* 38, 309.

Bridging international and social entrepreneurship in tourism. Case, the ViaVia Travelers Cafés.

*Dominique Vanneste
Jazmin Cevallos Vintimilla
University of Leuven
Belgium*

Introduction

Tourism and destination development can be fueled by very different, even opposing models and stakeholders. At the one end of the spectrum, one tends to consider the role of (international) private tourism investors who have the power to make a place into a destination and initiate advantages such as jobs and income for locals or learning opportunities while they have the power to tap into international markets. In those cases the focus is very much on economic benefits. The downsides such as power imbalances, leakage effects, precarious contracts and (or) alienation by locals from their place and culture among others, did pop up only in a later stage (Fortanier & van Wijk, 2010; Ioannides et al., 2021). At the other side of the spectrum, one can find -to some extent as a reaction to the previous- the model of community-based tourism development, dealing with tourism in function of the needs of the community, rather than the wishes of the tourists: 'tourism at the locals terms'. In many cases, this type of tourism is developed through projects, quite often projects financed by international organizations but the focus is on bottom-up dynamics, prioritizing participation and social as well as cultural, rather than economic sustainability, while moving away from (big or international) private investors and mass markets (Zapata et al., 2011; Adiyia et al., 2017). Only, once the project is completed and the money spend, the structure(s) put in place all too often tend to crumble or even fade away.

Tourism developments following a path in between these large-scale international private involvements and purely local, small-scale and vulnerable initiatives exist but are, nevertheless, far less examined. One of these options is Social Entrepreneurship (SE). SE looks quite promising as it takes into account the social aspects without denying the importance of profit. Especially in developing countries, SE is a rising alternative to traditional capitalist approaches of doing business that can serve as a leverage for economic, social, and environmental development. This does not mean that we understand this alternative fully and certainly not in the field of tourism. SE research has mainly focused on conceptualizing SE, far less on SE in tourism (TSE) and real life case studies. Therefore, the goal of our research was to identify if and how TSE can relate to aspects of sustainable tourism development *in practice* and the links with the *profile of the (international) investor*. In other words, we aim at looking for the potential of TSE to assume the bridging role between (international) private tourism development and sustainable entrepreneurship in tourism which contributes equally to the needs, dreams and expectations of travelers and locals and this, without turning a blind eye for its weaknesses.

To gain more insights in this TSE, we focus on what we consider an interesting (good?) practice, being the chain of ViaVia Travelers Cafés, created by a Belgian Tour Operator (Joker) in 1997. Its management firmly believes in the potential of tourism for sustainable development worldwide through social entrepreneurship. This does not mean that all is perfect. With a dynamic chain of 12 Cafés (2025) beyond Belgium and spread worldwide, the Belgian managers share an mission which implies to be a profit and social profit organization at the same time, while creating memorable and meaningful experiences for both visitors and locals, at a fair price/quality ratio and in a sustainable way (Elsen & Bekx, 2020). Our goal is to learn from their successes as well as from their mistakes, from their strengths and weaknesses. We investigated several ViaVia Cafés by interviewing the managers but our main target of investigation was the ViaVia Café at León (Nicaragua) since fieldwork allowed a deep understanding from thirty interviews gauging opinions and experiences from different stakeholder groups involved. Therefore, this paper will report on the ViaVia León learnings in the Results section while reflecting on generalization in the conclusions.

The structure of the paper is as follows. First, we will develop the concepts of SE and TSE, mainly starting with the insights of Dees, considered as the ‘father of SE’ (Stenn, 2017). Subsequently, we will explain our methodology and especially our coding of the transcripts in detail. The main bulk will, of course, concentrate on exploring how a foreign investor in tourism can contribute to local development while still being profitable, Dees being our lead to structure the different lessons learned. Finally, we will conclude by commenting the insights gained.

Conceptual framework

Social entrepreneurship

Over the past two decades, researchers have increasingly paid attention to the relatively new concept of social entrepreneurship (Rey-Martí et al., 2016). Social entrepreneurship (SE) usually refers to “business principles with a passion for social impact” (Wolk in Swanson & Zhang, 2012: 171). Although there is no single definition of social entrepreneurship, scholars have made several attempts to reach a conceptual definition concerning this subject. One way can be by identifying important parameters by placing organizations in a social spectrum (Swanson & Zhang, 2012), another by focusing on the differences between traditional entrepreneurship and SE (Bedi & Yadav, 2019; Martin & Osberg, 2007; Meyer et al., 2020; Maniam et al., 2018). In this study, we utilize the work of J. Greg Dees (1998) as a case to illustrate the practical implications of social entrepreneurship and explore its real-world application.

Dees, also referred to as “the father of SE” (Stenn, 2017) is often cited by other scholars who conceptualize SE (Abeysekera, 2019; Abu-Saifan, 2012; Martin & Osberg, 2007; Niño, 2015; Swanson & Zhang, 2012) because of his definition of social entrepreneurship. Dees’ work of 1998 combines an emphasis on discipline and accountability with the role of change agents in the social sector, defining SE through five ‘pillars’:

1. Social entrepreneurs “[adopt] a mission to create and sustain value (not just private value)”. This addresses the fact that social entrepreneurs should fundamentally embody a social mission of improvement, thereby aiming further than just making money or creating wealth. Longterm social impact is what they strive to achieve.
2. They recognize and “relentlessly [pursue] new opportunities to serve that mission”. Social entrepreneurs are characterized by their determination and willingness to achieve their social mission. In that respect, problems are not obstacles, but can be seen as opportunities.
3. Through social entrepreneurship “a process of continuous innovation, adaptation, and learning” is engaged. Social entrepreneurs are not inventors but creatively apply what others have invented. As such, their innovative nature is reflected in their modus operandi; it is not a onetime burst, but a continuous process of improving, adapting, and learning.
4. They “[act] boldly without being limited by resources currently in hand”. Social entrepreneurs do more with less; limited resources will not keep them from pursuing their vision. Therefore, they efficiently use resources, collaborate with others to leverage their opportunities, and take calculated risks to reduce harm when failures occur.
5. And lastly, social entrepreneurs “[exhibit] heightened accountability to the constituencies served and for the outcomes created”. This refers to the impact they would like to create by finding a close connection between all their stakeholders. They reinforce accountability and are result oriented.

Of course this definition did not stay without critics (REF) but elements are consistent to appear in other definitions.

Lubberinck (2019), based on Stenn (2017), acknowledged that social entrepreneurship can play an important role in addressing challenges faced by society. It is to this end more than just a business development option, but a key contributor to sustainable development (Stenn, 2017). It does so by addressing sustainability problems through innovative solutions (Mulder, 2007), incorporating elements that promote responsible consumption and production (Cornelius et al., 2008), mobilizing resources (Dees, 2001), and creating social impact. Consequently, SE may improve the well-being of local communities by addressing issues such as poverty (Zhang et al., 2022), education (Catherall & Richardson, 2017), healthcare (Amini et al., 2018), environmental degradation (Filatova & Gorbach, 2021), and clean energy (Becker et al., 2017). Additionally, SE often targets vulnerable groups in society, whose interwoven change in attitudes and behaviors nurtures their empowerment (Datta & Gailey, 2012; Haugh & Talwar, 2016; Perekrestova, 2022; Sepulveda et al., 2013 ; Dalimunthe et al., 2021). Especially in countries where governments do not prioritize gender equality and rural development, SE can foster a better life to disadvantaged groups and communities (Perekrestova, 2022).

It is worth noting that in academic literature criticism exists around social entrepreneurship. First of all, SE is not just the marketization of the non-profit sector? This extensive debate over whether social entrepreneurship actually belongs to the for- or non-profit sector is prominent in SE research. Some scholars

claim that social entrepreneurship is inherently part of the non-profit sector, as it is merely an application of entrepreneurial strategies to financially sustain non-profit organizations (Dempsey & Sanders, 2010; Lasprogata & Cotten, 2003). Others point out that SE's roots lay in entrepreneurship, and thus naturally belongs to the for profit sector (Ibáñez, 2022). It is clear that SE's spectrum encompasses characteristics of both non- and for-profit sector (Tan & Yoo, 2015), so choosing one side is altogether undesirable.

Further, it is true that innovation is an essential element of SE, but SE does not exclude working innovatively with already existing products and services. Sustainable Innovation emphasizes the newness of the process to meet unmet needs (Carvalho, 2016) which is not always valid for SE. Therefore, SE will not always reduce environmental impact (Underwood et al., 2012).

Finally, social entrepreneurship research faces some serious difficulties, of which one is a repetitive narrative. Dacin, Dacin and Tracey (2011) uncovered that social entrepreneurship research has a biased focus on heroic wins of individuals, creating an idealistic assumption that social entrepreneurs will somehow save the world. This view has limited research on the ability to learn from SE's failures, which can gain actually important insight (Margiono et al., 2019). SE research also faces theoretical and methodological dilemmas; even though scholars can agree to a certain point on what characteristics belong to SE, its absence of consensus complicates research and the accumulation of knowledge (Abu-Saifan, 2012). Also, questions arise on how to measure the intended social impact and its benefits due to its nonquantifiable, multicausal and temporal dimensions (Arogyaswamy, 2017; Austin et al., 2012; Barraket & Yousefpour, 2013).

Tourism Social Entrepreneurship

SE within tourism - tourism social entrepreneurship (TSE) - is at an initial stage (Mottiar & Boluk, 2017). Bridging the two concepts of SE and TSE is possible because of their overarching common goal: to eradicate social and economic problems through social and economic value creating activities (Altinay et al., 2016). Therefore, unlike traditional tourism ventures that tend to follow a profit-oriented capitalist approach with little regards to social aspects, TSE is a market driven approach that addresses social issues and minimizes negative impacts from the tourism industry (Aquino et al., 2018). They do so by mobilizing ideas, capacities, resources and social agreements for sustainable social transformation (Sheldon & Daniele, 2017).

TSE is said to lead to a more social and inclusive local development, as it often targets disadvantaged or excluded communities or individuals (Aquino et al., 2018). Notwithstanding the tendency to be primarily small to medium-sized entities (Dredge, 2017), studies have shown that TSE may improve livelihoods (Laeis & Lemke, 2016; Adiyia et al., 2017), enhance educational programs (Franzidis, 2019), and alleviate poverty (Adiyia & Vanneste, 2018; Zeng, 2018). Especially in developing countries, TSE can emerge as an important approach to alleviate a range of socio-economic and environmental issues that local governments fail to address (Dredge, 2017). Moreover, it creates a more sustainable tourism industry

(de Lange & Dodds, 2017). No doubt, TSE holds a great potential to serve as a vehicle for the sustainable development of communities (Aquino, 2022) but these idealized views cloud somewhat our understanding of realities while the issues with SE (section 2.1) are applicable to TSE as well.

There are few empirical studies that document the true extent of TSE, as case studies have not been substantially researched (Sheldon & Daniele, 2017). Further, there is a research gap on the overall evaluation processes of TSEs, because one tends to focus on the monetary impact TSEs create (Daye & Gill, 2017).

The ViaVia approach

The ViaVia Cafés are much more than a network of meeting places with some social and economic objectives. They not only (try to) act as a social enterprise; they have a mission statement based on the donut economy of Kate Raworth (2017) and embedded in a vision and philosophy of the ViaVia Tourism Academy (VVTA) which, in turn, is a unit within the Tour Operator Joker.

This implies “1) the making and implementing of long term projects that allow locals to get acquainted with sustainability in terms of their cultural, ecological and economic environment”, 2) “sharing knowledge and expertise”, 3) “setting up of and concretizing training and cooperation programs in the broad field of sustainable tourism”, 4) “organizing activities, thereby enabling contacts and initiatives with the ever-increasing multicultural world”, 5) “encouraging intercultural dialogue”, 6) “providing information”, 7) “organizing and/or guiding travel and intercultural exchanges” and 7) “awareness raising, research and education around the ideas of sustainable tourism” (VVTA, 2015) or , “[t]o contribute in a sustainable way to the dreams, needs and expectations of travelers and local partners, by creating meaningful and memorable travel and intercultural experiences.” (Via Via World, s.d.).

This implies also the use of a layered ‘observation model’ when a cultural audit is needed. Such an ‘audit’ is not meant to question local organizational structures but rather to reveal people’s incentives to fully commit to an organization, factors and power relations that make or break motivations as well as breaking points in different cultural settings. The layers succeed each other from ‘appearances’ (outer layer 5) focusing on external and visual cultural realities to ‘universal values’ (inner layer 1) being a rather intangible dimension that steers and molds an intercultural context (Elsen & Bekx, 2018: 73-74). Finally, VVTA follows a struct pla of 1. Development (stakeholder groups, management etc.), 2. Integration (mission, strategy, co-creation etc.), 3. Putting in place (concretize the goals – the 6P’s) and 4. Measuring (impact, self- assessment etc.). The interesting thing is that VVTA uses the basic 4 P’s (People, Planet, Prosperity and Partnership) and adds ‘Pleasure’, for the sake of tourism and ‘Peace’ for the sake of culture (Elsen & Bekx, 2018: 42-43).

In that respect ViaVia (VVTA and VV cafés) is not just the subject of our empirical research; it offers a real conceptual framework that can be used from a TSE perspective, across the tourism sector and in many cultural contexts.

Methodology

Why a focus on Latin America, Nicaragua, León

Despite a growing interest, studies on tourism social entrepreneurship (TSE) in Latin America remain limited (García Alonso et al., 2020) and with a specific geographic scope such as Mexico (Clausen, 2017; Gómez Díaz & Ramírez Melendez, 2021; Espinoza Sánchez et al. 2018, 2022; Saiz-Álvarez (2018)), Colombia (González-Cortés & Husain-Talero, 2020, Guasca et al., 2024), Ecuador (Lucas Mantuano et al. , 2019; Mendoza Macías & Loja Macías, 2018), or Chile (Zebryte & Jorquera, 2017). Not much is known about the landscape of social entrepreneurship in Nicaragua, and even less about SE in the tourism sector. Only one paper written by Franzidis (2019) examines a social business located in Granada, which happens to revolve around tourism.

VVTA has four ViaVia Cafés in Latin America: in Copán (Honduras), León (Nicaragua), Buenos Aires (Argentina) and Ayacucho (Peru). Nicaragua was chosen because of the opportunities for an in-depth and participative research while tourism is a key sector in Nicaragua's economy. Further, Nicaragua has been indicated as a well suited country for the implementation of SE (Cardoza, 2019). It is notable that the majority of these SEs are created and implemented by foreigners or Nicaraguans living abroad.

As in many other Latin-American countries (FAO & ECLAC, 2020), agriculture is the main driver for Nicaragua's economy. It is not only the major provider of employment (30% in general, 70% for rural Nicaragua), but accounts for 17% of the GDP and 70% of the export (World Bank et al., 2015). Despite its importance in the economy, current agricultural growth is still far below its full potential because of the national socio-economic context (World Bank et al., 2015). On top of that, agriculture faces the dangers of natural disasters and climate change (UNDP, 2010). Therefore, tourism plays a significant role in Nicaragua's economy and is an important sector for the country. By being a relatively inexpensive country to travel through and hosting a diverse range of natural landscapes, including surfers' beaches, volcanoes, lakes and rainforests, Nicaragua attracts tourists from all over the world. Besides the natural richness, the country also offers a unique cultural heritage, historic sites and colonial architecture. Tourism services are one of the main contributors to its gross domestic product (GDP), making up about 5.0% in 2022 (Travel and Tourism, being 7.6%; WTTC, 2023).

The primary law for tourism development, promotion and regulation is Law No. 306 (the 'General Tourism Law') (UNCTAD, 2013). This regulatory legislation, that was enacted in 1999, is carried out by INTUR and until recent also by ProNicaragua - a public-private organization that used to take care of business development in the tourism sector among others - but has been reformed to a new secretary that lies under direct supervision of the current government (Nicaragua Investiga, 2022).

Since its existence, it has boosted the local economy and improved tourism infrastructure with over 500 projects and over \$800 million of influx (UNCTAD, 2013). Moreover, the 'General Tourism Law' aims to safeguard historic monuments, sites, intangible heritage and their environment in a sustainable manner (UNESCO, s.d.).

Recent developments did not go without challenges and significant setbacks, particularly due to the 2018 political unrest and the COVID-19 pandemic, leading to a sharp decline in tourist arrivals (INTUR, 2021). Despite its natural wealth, Nicaragua remains one of the least developed countries in the region due to a history of civil conflicts and economic instability (IMF, 2023). With the dismantling of some civil society groups by the Ortega regime (UNHR, 2023), it is unknown how many *social* enterprises are still present and active in the country. In May 2022 a new law came into force that further restricts the functioning of civil society (United Nations, 2022). Under the disguise of preventing money laundering and financing of terrorism, this law imposes government's approval for all activities (complex registration process) while restricting funding and participation by foreign members involved in civil society organizations. This affected tourism as well. The tourist boom came to a halt in 2018 (Gallón, 2018). Although tourists were not banned or targeted, people might hesitate to visit the country. Up till today foreign instances do give a rather negative advice on travelling to Nicaragua. The US State department simply asks to reconsider travel plans (Travel.State.GOV) while e.g. the Belgian government advises to stay away from all meetings (Diplomatie.Belgium.be). This said, political issues are not a monopoly for Nicaragua and therefore Nicaraguan case can shed light on how to deal with them. Therefore, despite these issues, tourism has the potential to drive sustainable development while social entrepreneurship in this sector could help address Nicaragua's socio-economic challenges and support long-term growth (Franzidis, 2019; Lubberinck, 2019; UNCTAD, 2013).

As for León, the choice was determined by the fact that no other ViaVia Café could be found elsewhere in Nicaragua, except for León. This is a deliberate choice of VVTA for its cafés since they always opt for an urban environment with a heritage value. This is often not a capital but a major city that allows encounters between tourists and locals while a supply (by local suppliers) of visits and experiences in an urban as well as in a (surrounding) natural environment is available.

A participative research and a qualitative methodology

During the field work, the first author stayed at the ViaVia Café, using a participative observation method. She immersed herself in various activities revolving around the operation of ViaVia León (VVL) and got to know staff and other stakeholders (visitors, performers) in an informal way -without hiding the purpose of the stay- up to the point that a formal and fully open interview with informed consent could take place (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Surveyed subjects and stakeholders (own design).

To uncover information on a number of specific research topics, semi-structured interviews were used. The semi-structured interviews (protocols) were adapted according to relevant target groups and their relationship with VVL (Figure 2). Adjustments could be made during the data collection when needed, as well as pursuing in-depth questions on opinions and perceptions. The protocols for the semi-structured interviews were set up by the research team, sometimes adjusted with the support of one of the managers. The leading themes are summarized in Table 1.

The fieldwork experience in León, Nicaragua took place from October to December 2022. All interviews aimed to seek insights and understanding on how VVL, the case study in question, relates to social entrepreneurship and sustainability. This resulted in 30 interviews with the VVL managers, employees, tourists, locals, an associated tourism agency (Volcano Day), and a NGO (Auténtico vzw). These interviews ranged from half an hour up to four hours, and went smoothly, with many of the participants appearing happy to contribute. All performed interviews - except for the managers and head of the associated NGO - were undertaken in Spanish with no translator. The managers' and NGO's interviews were performed, instead, in other languages such as English or Dutch. All interviews in this stage were conducted in person. Despite efforts, the research lacks the perspectives from some key stakeholders: the most important being the national tourism institute (INTUR). Interviews were denied, limiting insights into the government's view on social enterprises. While this represents a limitation, it indicates how relationships are not always running smoothly, while all stakeholders are careful with what to do or what to say.

As mentioned before, upon arrival in Nicaragua, associated stakeholders of VVL (employees, NGO, tourism agency) were briefed by the VVL managers on the reason of research. For the remaining interviewees, being with locals and tourists, the researcher introduced the aim. Prior to the start of each interview, participants were informed on the goal, set up and process of the study. In this briefing, it was made clear that participants' anonymity was guaranteed, and that they were free to elaborate as much as they felt comfortable with. At the end of the interview, participants had the opportunity to share other insights or information and ask questions. The interviews were recorded and transcribed, resulting in 210 pages of transcripts of which 57 from interviews with the managers and 153 pages from interviews with other stakeholders (staff, tourists, locals and 1 NGO).

The interview protocols and analysis schemes incorporated seven large themes based on literature (e.g. Dees, 1998) and the mission statement of Via Via which helped and steered deductive coding while new (induced) codes, based on new and unexpected information (e.g. corruption) were limited but added if considered useful (**Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**).

Table 2: Coding scheme (own design)

Theme		Codes
Social entrepreneurship	Social mission with social values	Diversity - Connectivity – Opportunities - Intercultural entrepreneurship - Sustainable tourism
	Innovation, adaptation, and learning	Learning moments – Innovation – Adaptation -Policy/strategy
	Acting boldly without being limited by resources currently in hand	Resources - Partnerships - Finances - Corruption - Conflicts - Failures
	Exhibiting heightened accountability to the constituencies served and for the outcomes created	Accountability - Impact on employees - Impact on clients - Impact on locals - Impact of employees on ViaVia - Impact of tourists on ViaVia - Impact of locals on ViaVia
Sustainable development	Economic development	Welfare – Creating jobs - Finances
	Social development	Discrimination/inclusion – Education – Gender - Diminishing poverty - Partnerships
	Environmental protection	Local products and services – Sustainability norms – Food – Plastic – Recycling – Energy – Water – Sustainable transport

As mentioned before, our aim was to go somewhat beyond ViaVia León by testing our results against the opinion of other ViaVia Café managers. We talked to 7 of them, resulting in another 100 pages of transcripts. These interviews allowed some

generalization as well as contributed to deeper understanding and therefore to reliability.

In order to improve rigor and fuel consistency, the first author coded the transcripts according to a strict scheme of mainly deduced codes and created a set of interpretations, supported by citations from the transcripts. The second author, who read the entire set of transcripts as well, commented and challenged them during a series of discussions, until agreement was reached.

Results and discussion

We use some themes mentioned by Dees (1998) as a lead.

Adopting a mission to create and sustain value

ViaVia León (VVL) aligns with the social mission of its parent organization by embracing interculturality, diversity, and fostering social inclusion, meeting Dees' definition of social entrepreneurship as "creating and sustaining social value" (Dees, 1998). VVL's motto, "cada cabeza es un mundo" (*every mind contains its own world*), highlights its commitment to respecting diverse perspectives and supporting its employees. They try to facilitate this process on a small scale and through a spontaneous process.

"In my mind, ViaVia's mission [is] to provide a place where everyone feels welcome. [...] A place where people can learn from each other. A Nicaraguan who sits next to a foreigner at the bar and spends a whole afternoon drinking beer, rum or whatever, and at the end of the day or evening knows how many brothers or sisters they each have, what their job is, how much they earn, so to speak,... actually learn from each other." (Manager 1 ViaVia León)

To achieve its mission, VVL organizes various cross-cultural activities, such as 'trivia nights' supporting charity, free concerts featuring local bands, and cultural events like poetry readings and dance performances,. They promote local customs through its 'wall of myths.' That these activities indeed foster intercultural exchange between foreigners and locals, is confirmed by both the tourists and locals:

"It was basically me and mostly people who are living there. And, I had that kind of experience once also in Guatemala, where you're just surrounded by the locals and it's just a different vibe, that's for sure, because they are there to have fun. Obviously, the travelers are there to have fun as well, but they're there in another way. They're kind of in their hometown. They're not, like, seeing it all for the first time. They're there because they genuinely like it." (Tourist_3)

"I do feel that there is that cultural exchange because several times that I was going [...] it was with local friends. But as I got to know more people, in this case German people, people from Belgium, from the United States, and different countries... I keep having the different cultural exchange, anecdotes and things that happen in their country they get to tell there. Different ways of celebrating, even different ways of consuming alcohol or food. So, I do feel that there is a great intercultural impact between the local people and the people who visit us." (Local _2)

Intercultural exchange occurs not only between tourists and locals but also among staff, with Belgian managers working alongside Nicaraguan employees. This blend of work allows for the sharing of customs and practices within the hospitality sector,

a feature common across ViaVia Travelers cafés, where Belgian ownership often pairs with local staff and experience. VVL's commitment to sustainable tourism is further reinforced by its partnership with Volcano Day, a social enterprise focusing on empowering local talent and organizing eco-friendly trips that respect nature, pay fair wages to locals, and bridge cultures. They were granted space for their office at the VVL location.

Engaging in a process of continuous innovation, adaptation, and learning

It is difficult to value commitment to continuous innovation, adaptation, and learning, despite being an innovative social enterprise in Nicaragua. While the partnership with Volcano Day and offering a diverse (world kitchen) menu in León are considered innovative, VVL's efforts towards ongoing innovation appear limited. However, innovation often lies in small things, taking into account that social enterprises (entrepreneurs) are not very popular from a government's point of view. Moreover, during the 2018 political upheaval and the COVID-19 pandemic, VVL remained open while not being profitable in that period, offering financial support to employees, and utilizing the Belgian ViaVia/JOKER network for assistance, demonstrating resilience in the face of crises. This was a deliberate decision and policy as was mentioned by one of the managers. This might not be a real 'innovation' but it certainly went against the mainstream trend at the time.

"Profit is super important and without more profit the ViaVia in León is going to fade away quietly [...]. But in times of crisis and during the pandemic, profit should not take precedence alone. The bottom line is that so many businesses in León have simply shut the door and left people without severance pay. I'm not going to call out names, but there are businesses here from down the street where a night guard arrived with an air conditioning unit and wanted to sell it to me because they left there with a lot of back pay, no liquidation, no vacation... [they] received nothing. We don't do that. Of course, there are limits to that because we are not an NGO. We must try to make a profit, but at times of crisis it is not our main goal, [...] even then we do try, with the help of the network in Belgium, to help people who have always worked for us in any way that we can." (Manager_1 ViaVia León)

Furthermore, VVL demonstrates flexibility and a willingness to experiment, allowing it to swiftly respond to external shocks, as noted by Dobson et al. (2018). For instance, during the COVID-19 pandemic, VVL introduced the "café corona," offering affordable coffee to locals (who previously benefited from free coffee) but at a far lower price than other venues.

Some issues are difficult to resolve. VVL faces challenges from government policies and corruption in Nicaragua. The regime's lack of awareness of VVL's social entrepreneurship status and the fact that they keep on a low profile is a blessing. Yet the friction between the government and civil society organisations (UNHR, 2023) poses risks, as does the political climate that complicates compliance with legalities and affecting operations:

"I think, in that area it has modernized, also become stricter, more controls. [...] Grave corruption was never possible. But minor corruption, yes, and that used to be obvious. But that has actually all gone [...], which is not to say that if, so to speak, if a problem arises..." (Manager_2 ViaVia León)

It's a tricky balancing act for VVL, but the fact that this Travelers Café is still present in Nicaragua more than 20 years, shows the ability to learn how to deal with this exogenous pressure. This 'diplomacy' act, as such, is probably the most important learning process for VVL.

Acting boldly without being limited or steered by resources currently in hand

Dees' third criterion for social enterprises (SEs) emphasizes that they should not be limited by their available resources, encouraging efficient use of assets and collaboration. ViaVia León (VVL) benefits from renting its premises from the ViaVia network, which has provided financial stability during difficult times, although its revenue remains relatively modest compared to similar establishments. VVL focuses on social value creation through partnerships, such as its collaboration with Volcano Day for sustainable tourism and various charitable initiatives, but it has faced setbacks from past failures and management changes that have impacted its charitable commitments.

As for the natural resources, they are valorized well through Volcano Day, presenting visitors a full experience which goes beyond exploring (seeing) nature.

"[...]So, I really got to know people from different countries, just at those couple of hours. I got to see Nicaragua and nature, the volcanoes, volcano boarding. On the way [to Cerro Negro], we were talking to each other, we were listening to music. We were exchanging music. We got to see nature." (Tourist_3)

Exhibiting a heightened accountability to the constituencies served and for the outcomes created

When it comes down to the impact created to their staff, employees mention that their lives have changed positively because of the economic improvement in their livelihoods (Employee_2, 6, 8, 10, 13) it has opened their view on the world (Employee_3, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16), they have gained new skills (Employee_1, 5, 10, 13), learned how to stand up for themselves (Employee_6, 9, 11), or experience VVL as a place they can call home (Employee_7, 9, 16).

Also, when looking at gender, we find that a slim majority of employees at VVL are women. This stands in line with the overall tourism sector in Nicaragua and is a positive trend to be used as a tool for empowerment. One employee mentioned VVL helped to escape from domestic abuse.

"I went through a process of violence with my former partner. [...] When I came here to work, they gave me the opportunity, I repeat, to work. To perform, to progress. [...] I feel good working here. I feel that I have made friends, I am getting to know people that perhaps in that world where I was, I didn't have the opportunity to go out, but today I do. Today I can tell you that I live a stable life, a complex life, a life that I never imagined I would live" (Female Employee_11)

For the tourists, VVL serves as a valuable platform for relationship-building and cultural exchange, contributing to an authentic experience in Nicaragua that highlights local engagement. As banal it might look, the pool table at VVL serves as a key element for fostering intercultural interactions, helping to break down stereotypes between locals and tourists. Tourists influence VVL's identity, as it has

become known as a gathering spot for foreigners, despite many not being aware of its social mission before arriving in León. Additionally, VVL adapts to bridge between sustainability, tourist expectations and respect for local norms and customs. Being very strict about dropping tours to cockfighting venues while avoiding hurtful criticism, is a good example.

“So [we] take the tourists to a suburb where they would never come on their own. [...] We did that for a very long time, every Sunday. Not to make money from it, not at all. But that is something that is less evident today than it was before, [because of the cockfighting] exist[ing] here. [...] I don't think we, as white people, should start condemning cockfighting here in Nicaragua. Leave that to the Nicaraguans.” (Manager_2)

Trying to show accountability was quite obvious with Volcano Day and has been highly beneficial for both entities. Future expansions of their collaboration are anticipated. In contrast, the relationship with the NGO Auténtico is less impactful. Auténtico, a Belgian non-profit organization that aims to improve the living conditions of slums in and around León, has some ties with VVL, as the latter helped design a garden in Auténtico's educational center in El Tamarindo. Yet, this partnership is not embedded in the operations of VVL and further collaboration has not materialized, thereby limiting the potential for social value creation despite the resources available.

Conclusions

This case study of ViaVia León sheds light on the achievements as well as on the difficulties experienced by a TSE and allows us to bring down the idealistic focus on heroic wins which is often the case when dealing with (T)SE. It shows a more truthful, balanced view on the complexity of SEs. Dacin et al. (2011) put it even stronger stating that this idealism (surrounding the concept) should be recognized as a problem in SE research; focusing (more) on the possible pitfalls could help to adapt and ensure success for (T)SE research and practice. This is exactly what we aimed for while analyzing the model of ViaVia Cafés, showing that a TSE fueled by an international tourism investor can act as a catalyst for sustainable (tourism) development and can even set standards, without a denial or neglect of local needs, culture and skills.

Of course, the lessons learned from one case study cannot be generalized. Nevertheless, the fact that we checked our conclusions with the managers of other ViaVia Cafés (ViaVia Copán, Honduras; Entebbe, Uganda; Kathmandu, Nepal; Buenos Aires, Argentina; Guereo, Senegal; Yogyakarta, Indonesia; Harganat, Mongolia; Ayacucho, Peru; Marrakesh, Morocco) is reassuring since we got confirmed our results over and over again. This does not mean that the same approach can be copied everywhere. The political and cultural environments play a decisive part. We can give two examples. In Latin-America, talking about sexuality and feminism with (female) staff is possible while in a Muslim context, this is not working as was mentioned about a workshop with staff and locals where some participants said: *'Feminism? We don't want that. That's not us; that's dirty, those aren't fine women'* (ViaVia Indonesia). The ViaVia managers try to provide some social security for their employees, among others, because social security is a taken-for-granted element in Belgian society but even with the best intentions,

this does not work everywhere as was mentioned by ViaVia Nepal: “We are planning to make a contribution for our employees, but [...] when they go and get money from the social security fund, they say you have to go to ten different places to get ten different signatures, get a form to fill out... [therefore] we will have to wait and see.” (ViaVia Nepal).

In summary, the main insights are the following:

The ViaVia Cafés represent an excellent and feasible model that indeed bridges between the approach of an international investment/investor (in tourism), respect for the needs and wants of the locals, and a joyful experience for the visitors. The ViaVia Travelers Cafés are indeed an example of the integration of profit orientation and concerns for social and ecological aspects, a preview of how TSE can work, based on a well-grounded vision and mission and a choice for a low profile and small scale as a foreign investor.

This does not exclude threatening challenges such as:

- Although the mission of this TSE should be carried out in the same way by all premises worldwide, the elements of the vision and mission should/must be translated into practice in a unique way for each premise as to be successful or even survive.
- The beneficiaries from a TSE might be limited, e.g. to ‘only’ the staff and some associated tourism agencies of the ViaVia Cafés; to gain real impact, broader (institutionalized) partnerships might be needed which, in turn, can threaten the participative approach and equal focus on visitors and community; one constantly has to look for and/or monitor a delicate balance.
- Contributions to achieving sustainability highly depend on insights into the available tourism supply, infrastructure and the political landscape of a (host) country; a correct assessment of ways to handle (diverse) cultural values is not obvious and can threaten clear and straight forward decision making in (tourism) product as well as destination development.

The lack of collaboration from national authorities is very obvious in this case as e.g. the national tourism institute (INTUR) refused to participate. This is not unusual, although in the case of Nicaragua, the government's critical stance towards SEs and civil society in general, is very pronounced and leads to an atmosphere of uncertainty and concern. This indicates that Social Enterprises are more vulnerable and easier to target than companies that attach little importance to their social impact. This case therefore shows that striking a balance between staying true to one's mission and finding an answer to issues resulting from a particular political and social spectrum is extremely important and a characteristic of a successful SE.

We were impressed by the theoretical and conceptual grounding of VVTA of which the ViaVia Café network is a part, reflected in several publications (Elsen, 2011; Elsen and Bekx, 2018, 2020). This in turn underlines the importance of the personal factor in transmitting a vision and position taking (of its CEO) into an inspiring drive of the TSE as an organization. During the research, Via Via

provide(d) the researchers with some insights on how to bridge between the principles on (T)SE (on the one hand) and practice (on the other hand). The missing link of smart operationalization is not spectacular but avoids 'social washing'. The thoughtfulness of ViaVia according to location, scale, communication, management style and loyalty to mission and values, shows a choice to consider very carefully its expansion, geographically and in terms of local partner networks. Therefore, more cases are needed with a focus on the ways to internalize the SE concept in the DNA of a company or organization and to operationalize (in tourism) the (T)SE concept in terms of a practical implementation, while ViaVia seems a very interesting point of reference.

References

- Abeysekera, R. (2019). Social Entrepreneurship: Concepts and Research Areas. *Sri Lanka Journal of Management Studies*, 1(2), 29–42. <https://doi.org/10.4038/sljms.v1i2.47>
- Abu-Saifan, S. (2012). Social Entrepreneurship: Definition and Boundaries. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 2, 22–27. <https://doi.org/10.22215/timreview523>
- Adiyia, B., De Rademaeker, S., Vanneste, D., & Manyisa Ahebwa, W. (2017). Understanding local entrepreneurship and small enterprises in the tourism–development nexus: The case of western Uganda. *Development Southern Africa* 34 (1): 105-120. DOI: 10.1080/0376835X.2016.1259991
- Adiyia, B., & Vanneste, D., (2018). Local tourism value chain linkages as pro-poor tools for regional development in western Uganda. *Development Southern Africa* 35 (2): 210-224. DOI: [10.1080/0376835X.2018.1428529](https://doi.org/10.1080/0376835X.2018.1428529)
- Altinay, L., Sigala, M., & Waligo, V. (2016). Social Value Creation through Tourism Enterprise. *Tourism Management*, 54, 404–417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2015.12.011>
- Amini, Z., Arasti, Z., & Bagheri, A. (2018). Identifying Social Entrepreneurship Competencies of Managers in Social Entrepreneurship Organizations in Healthcare Sector. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 8(19), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40497-018-0102-x>
- Aquino, R. S., Lück, M., & Schänzel, H. A. (2018). Tourism Social Entrepreneurship for 52 Sustainable Community Development: Review and Conceptual Framework. In T. Young, P. Stolk, & G. McGinnis (eds.), *CAUTHE 2018: Get Smart: Paradoxes and Possibilities in Tourism, Hospitality and Events Education and Research* (pp. 369–379). The University of Newcastle. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2018.09.001>
- Aquino, R. S. (2022). Community Change through Tourism Social Entrepreneurship. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 95, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2022.103442>
- Arogyaswamy, B. (2017). Social Entrepreneurship Performance Measurement: A Time-Based Organizing Framework. *Business Horizons*, 60, 603–611. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2017.05.004>
- Austin, J., Stevenson, H., & Wei-Skillern, J. (2012). Social and commercial entrepreneurship: same, different, or both? *Revista de Administração*, 47(3), 370–384. <https://doi.org/10.5700/rausp1055>

- Barraket, J., & Yousefpour, N. (2013). Evaluation and Social Impact Measurement Amongst Small to Medium Social Enterprises: Process, Purpose and Value. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 72(4), 447–458. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8500.12042>
- Becker, S., Kunze, C., & Vancea, M. (2017). Community energy and social entrepreneurship: Addressing purpose, organisation and embeddedness of renewable energy projects. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 147, 25–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.01.048>
- Bedi, H. S., & Yadav, N. (2019). Social Entrepreneurship: A Conceptual Clarity. *Our Heritage*, 67(10), 1006–1016. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3541919>
- Cardoza, F. (2019). Felipe Symmes: “Hay un campo fértil para el emprendimiento social en Nicaragua.” *Revista 360°*, 35–37.
- Carvalho, J. M. S. (2016). Social Innovation and Entrepreneurship: The Case of Porto Region. In A. Briones, S. Galina, I. Purcarea, & A. Backx Noronha Viana (eds.), *Handbook of Research on Entrepreneurial Success and its Impact on Regional Development* (pp. 539–573). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-1923-2.ch036>
- Catherall, R., & Richardson, M. (2017). *Social entrepreneurship in education - Empowering the next generation to address society's needs*. British Council.
- Clausen, H. B. (2017). Social Entrepreneurship and Tourism Development in Mexico: A Case Study of North American Social Entrepreneurs in a Mexican Town. In P. J. Sheldon & R. Daniele (eds.), *Social Entrepreneurship and Tourism - Philosophy and Practice* (pp. 195–205). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-46518-0_11
- Cornelius, N., Todres, M., Janjuha-Jivraj, S., Woods, A., & Wallace, J. (2008). Corporate social responsibility and the social enterprise. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 81(2), 355–370. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-007-9500-7>
- Dacin, M. T., Dacin, P. A., & Tracey, P. (2011). Social Entrepreneurship: A Critique and Future Directions. *Organization Science*, 22(5), 1203–1213. <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.1100.0620>
- Dalimunthe, H. H. B., Sutisna, A., Karnadi, K., Retnowati, E., & Tijari, A. (2021). Social Entrepreneurship Empowerment in the Indonesian Archipelagic Communities. *Indonesian Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship*, 7(2), 103–110. <https://doi.org/10.17358/ijbe.7.2.103>
- Datta, P. B., & Gailey, R. (2012). Empowering Women Through Social Entrepreneurship: Case Study of a Women's Cooperative in India. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 36(3), 569–587. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6520.2012.00505.x>
- Daye, M., & Gill, K. (2017). Social Enterprise Evaluation: Implications for Tourism Development. In P. J. Sheldon & R. Daniele (eds.), *Social Entrepreneurship and Tourism - Philosophy and Practice* (pp. 173–192). Springer International Publishing.

- Dees, J. G. (1998). The Meaning of “Social Entrepreneurship” . Kauffman Center for Entrepreneurial Leadership. 6p.
https://www.academia.edu/1071839/The_meaning_of_social_entrepreneurship
- Dees, J. G. (2001). Social Entrepreneurship: Mobilizing Resources for Success. The Grantsmanship Center, 800, 1–14. <https://www.tgci.com/articles/social-entrepreneurshipmobilizing-resources-success>
- de Lange, D., & Dodds, R. (2017). Increasing sustainable tourism through social entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29(7), 1977–2002. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-02-2016-0096>
- Dempsey, S. E., & Sanders, M. L. (2010). Meaningful work? Nonprofit marketization and work/life imbalance in popular autobiographies of social entrepreneurship. *Organization*, 17(4), 437–459. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1350508410364198>
- Dobson, K., Boone, S., Andries, P., & Daou, A. (2018). Successfully creating and scaling a sustainable social enterprise model under uncertainty: The case of ViaVia Travellers Cafés. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 172, 4555–4564.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.09.010>
- Dredge, D. (2017). Institutional and Policy Support for Tourism Social Entrepreneurship. In P. J. Sheldon & R. Daniele (eds.), *Social Entrepreneurship and Tourism* (pp. 35–56). Springer 56 International Publishing. http://books.google.com.co/books?id=-RJCMQAACAAJ&dq=intitle:Social+Entrepreneurship+and+Tourism&hl=&cd=4&source=gbs_api%0Apapers3://publication/uuid/86CA9509-2D7B-4645-A125-EE04809352A9
- Espinoza Sánchez, R., Morales Martínez, D. M., Larmat González, R. L., & Cornejo Ortega, J.L. (2018). Los Eprendimientos Sociales Turísticos Como Estrategia para el Desarrollo Local Endógeno. Caso “Canopy el Indio” y el “Chorillo”. *TURyDES*, 11 (24).
<https://www.eumed.net/rev/curydes/24/emprendimientos-turisticos-desarrollo.html>
- Espinoza Sánchez, R., Peña Casillas, C. S., & Cornejo Ortega, J. L. (2022). Impact of the 4 Helix Model on the Sustainability of Tourism Social Entrepreneurships in Jalisco and Nayarit, Mexico. *Sustainability*, 14(636), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14020636>
- Elsen, B. (2011). *Joker Grensverleggend Ondernemen. De wereld als speelveld*. Leuven, Uitgeverij Van Halewyck.
- Elsen, B. & Bekx, N. (2018). Reis naar duurzaam ondernemen met de SDGs als kompas. Mechelen, Trendbookx.
- Elsen, B. & Bekx, N. (2020). *Travel towards sustainable entrepreneurship*. Mechelen, Trendhuis.
- FAO, & ECLAC. (2020). *Food systems and COVID-19 in Latin America and the Caribbean: Trade performance during the crisis. Bulletin 12*.
- Filatova, U., & Gorbach, O. (2021). Ecology-oriented social entrepreneurship: Analysis of waste management legal regulation in Russia. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 937, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/937/4/042050>

- Fortanier, F., & van Wijk, J. (2010). Sustainable tourism industry development in sub-Saharan Africa: Consequences of foreign hotels for local employment. *International Business Review*, 19 (2), 191-205 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2009.11.007>
- Franzidis, A. (2019). An examination of a social tourism business in Granada, Nicaragua. *Tourism Review*, 74(6), 1179–1190. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TR-04-2017-0076>
- García Alonso, R., Thoene, U., Figueroa, A. M., & Murillo Amaris, E. (2020). Social entrepreneurship in the pacific alliance. *REVESCO. Revista de Estudios Cooperativos*, 133, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.5209/REVE.67341>
- Gómez Diaz, J., & Ramírez Melendez, M. (2021). Emprendimientos Turísticos, una Alternative de Desarrollo en Comunidades Cercanas a Centros Integrals Planeados. Caso Bahías de Huatulco, México. *Revista De Ciencias Sociales*, 171, 189–201.
- González-Cortés, L. D., & Husain-Talero, S. (2020). Social Entrepreneurship and Sustainable Tourism in Colombia: A Baseline Study in Post-conflict Regions. *The International Journal of Social Sustainability in Economic, Social and Cultural Context*, 16(2), 65–85.
- Guasca, M., Van Broeck, AM., Vanneste, D. (2024). Tourism and the elusive peace amid violent post-conflict geographies in Colombia. *Tourism Geographies*, 26(7), 1072-1088. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616688.2022.2162574>
- Haugh, H. M., & Talwar, A. (2016). Linking Social Entrepreneurship and Social Change: The Mediating Role of Empowerment. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 133, 643–658. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-014-2449-4>
- Ibáñez, M. J. (2022). Social entrepreneurship review: a gap in the Latin American context. *Management Research*, 20(1), 6–24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRJIAM-09-2021-1232>.
- IMF (International Monetary Fund). (2023). Facilitating International Bond Market Access in Nicaragua. https://www.imf.org/external/np/ins/english/capacity_countries_mfs_nicaragua.htm
- INTUR. (2021). Boletín de Estadísticas de Turismo Año 2020 (Vol. 31). <https://www.intur.gob.ni/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Bolet%C3%ADn-de-Estad%C3%ADsticas-de-Turismo-de-Nicaragua-del-A%C3%B1o-2020-nic.pdf>
- Ioannides, D.; Gyimóthy, S.; James, L. From Liminal Labor to Decent Work: A Human-Centered Perspective on Sustainable Tourism Employment. *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 851. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13020851>
- Laeis, G. C. M., & Lemke, S. (2016). Social entrepreneurship in tourism: applying sustainable livelihoods approaches. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 28(6), 1076–1093. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-05-2014-0235>
- Lasprogata, G. A., & Cotten, M. N. (2003). Contemplating “Enterprise”: The Business and Legal Challenges of Social Entrepreneurship. *American Business Law Journal*, 41(1), 67–113. <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-1714.2003.tb00002.x>
- Lubberinck, R. (2019). Social Entrepreneurship and Sustainable Development. In *Decent Work and Economic Growth* (pp. 1–11). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003042396-3>

- Lucas Mantuano, C. A., Salazar Olives, G., & Loor Caicedo, C. K. (2019). El emprendimiento social en el turismo comunitario de la provincia de Manabí, Ecuador. *Telos: Revista de Estudios Interdisciplinarios En Ciencias Sociales*, 21(3), 661–680.
- Maniam, B., Engel, J., & Subramaniam, G. (2018). Examining the Significance and Impact of Social Entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7(4.38), 818– 824. <https://doi.org/10.14419/ijet.v7i4.38.27552>
- Margiono, A., Kariza, A., & Heriyati, P. (2019). Venture legitmiimacy and storytelling in social enterprises. *Small Enterprise Research*, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13215906.2019.1570318>
- Martin, R. L., & Osberg, S. (2007). Social entrepreneurship: the case for definition. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, 28–39. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201310158>
- Mendoza Macías, M., & Loja Macías, S. (2018). Emprendimientos sociales: turismo en la costa ecuatoriana Social entrepreneurship: tourism in the Ecuadorian coast. *Revista Academia & Negocios*, 4(1), 81–92. <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=560863073009>
- Meyer, C. R., Cohen, D. G., & Gauthier, J. (2020). Social entrepreneurship, stakeholder management, and the multiple fitness elements of sustainability: where cash is no longer king. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, 32(5), 431–455. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08276331.2019.1661614>
- Mottiar, Z., & Boluk, K. (2017). Understanding How Social Entrepreneurs Fit into the Tourism Discourse. In P. Sheldon & R. Danielle (eds.), *Social Entrepreneurship and Tourism: Philosophy and Practice* (pp. 117–132). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-46518-0_7
- Mulder, K. F. (2007). Innovation for Sustainable Development: From environmental design to transition management. *Sustainability Science*, 2, 253–263. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-007-0036-7>
- Nicaragua Investiga. (2022). *Régimen cierra ProNicaragua y crea Secretaría de Promoción de Inversión y Exportación*. <https://nicaraguainvestiga.com/economia/98828-regimen-cierra-pronicaragua-y-crea-secretaria/>
- Niño, A. C. S. (2015). Social Entrepreneurship and Corporate Social Responsibility: Differences and Points in Common. *Journal of Business & Economic Policy*, 2(2), 85–93
- Perekrestova, V. (2022). Normative coherence through social entrepreneurship: Fostering women’s empowerment in Myanmar. *Development Policy Review*, 40(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dpr.12627>
- Raworth, K. (2017). *Doughnut Economics. Seven Ways to Think Like a 21st-Century Economist*. Penquin Random House.
- Rey-Martí, A., Ribeiro-Soriano, D., & Palacios-Marqués, D. (2016). A bibliometric analysis of social entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Research*, 69, 1651–1655. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2015.10.033>
- Saiz-Álvarez, J. M. (2018). Turismo sostenible y emprendimiento social. El pueblo mágico de Tequila, México. *Retos*, 8(15), 51–68. <https://doi.org/10.17163/ret.n15.2018.04>

- Sepulveda, L., Syrett, S., & Calvo, S. (2013). Social enterprise and ethnic minorities: exploring the consequences of the evolving British policy agenda. *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy*, 31(4), 633–648. <https://doi.org/10.1068/c11319>
- Sheldon, P. J., & Daniele, R. (2017). Social Entrepreneurship and Tourism - Philosophy and Practice. In *Social Entrepreneurship and Tourism - Philosophy and Practice*. Springer International Publishing
- Stenn, T. L. (2017). *Social Entrepreneurship as Sustainable Development - Introducing the Sustainability Lens*. Springer Nature.
- Swanson, L. A., & Zhang, D. D. (2012). Social entrepreneurship. In T. Burger-Helmchen (ed.), *Entrepreneurship, Gender, Geographies and Social Context*. (pp. 171–190). Rijeka: InTech. <https://doi.org/10.35120/kij34010241s>
- Tan, W.-L., & Yoo, S.-J. (2015). Social Entrepreneurship Intentions of Nonprofit Organizations. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship*, 6(1), 103–125. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19420676.2014.954260>
- UNCTAD. (2013). *Services Policy Review – Nicaragua*. https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/ditctncd2013d13_en.pdf
- Underwood, S., Blundel, R., Lyon, F., & Schaefer, A. (2012). Introduction to Social and Sustainable Enterprise: Changing the Nature of Business. In S. Underwood, R. Blundel, F. Lyon, & A. Schaefer (eds.), *Social and Sustainable Enterprise: Changing the Nature of Business. Contemporary Issues in Entrepreneurship Research* (Vol.2). Bradford: Emerald. [https://doi.org/10.1108/s2040-7246\(2012\)0000002004](https://doi.org/10.1108/s2040-7246(2012)0000002004)
<https://oro.open.ac.uk/35631/1/Underwood%20et%20al.%202012%20Social%20and%20Sustainable%20Enterprise%20-%20Introduction%20chapter.pdf>
- UNDP. (2010). *Mainstreaming Climate Change in Nicaragua*. <https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/publications/es/CC%20risk%20Mainstreaming%20Climate%20Change%20in%20Nicaragua%20ENG.pdf>
- UNESCO. (s.d.). *Ley 306 ley de incentivos para la industria turística de la república de Nicaragua*. <https://www.unesco.org/es/cultnatlaws/ley-306-ley-de-incentivos-para-la-industria-turistica-de-la-republica-de-nicaragua>
- United Nations. (2022). *Nicaragua: New law heralds damaging crackdown on civil society, UN warns*. <https://news.un.org/en/story/2022/05/1117802>
- UNHR. (2023). *Nicaragua: Crimes against humanity being committed against civilians for political reasons, investigation says*. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/pressreleases/2023/03/nicaragua-crimes-against-humanity-being-committed-against-civilians>
- VVTA (ViaVia Tourism Academy). (2015). *Mission Statement ViaVia Tourism Academy*. (internal document)
- Via Via World. (s.d.). *Our story*. <https://viavia.world/nl/our-story/> retrieved 2023
- World Bank, IFAD, & Cooperación Suiza en América Central. (2015). *Agriculture in Nicaragua: Performance, Challenges, and Options*. <https://doi.org/10.1596/25978>

<https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/532131485440242670/pdf/102989-WP-P152101-Box394848B-OUO-9.pdf>

WTTC (World Travel & Tourism Council). (2023). *Travel & Tourism Economic Impact 2023. Nicaragua*. https://assets-global.website-files.com/6329bc97af73223b575983ac/647ef6ac73fc243bcc111c1a_EIR2023-Nicaragua.pdf

Zapata, M.J., Hall, C. M., Lindo, P., Vanderschaeghe, M. (2011). Can community-based tourism contribute to development and poverty alleviation? Lessons from Nicaragua. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 14 (8), 725-749.

Zebryte, I., & Jorquera, H. (2017). Chilean tourism sector “B Corporations”: evidence of social entrepreneurship and innovation. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 23(6), 866–879. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEER-07-2017-0218>

Zeng, B. (2018). How can social enterprises contribute to sustainable pro-poor tourism development? *Chinese Journal of Population Resources and Environment*, 16(2), 159–170. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10042857.2018.1466955>

Zhang, X., Sun, Y., Gao, Y., & Dong, Y. (2022). Paths out of poverty: Social entrepreneurship and sustainable development. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13(November), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1062669>

What is ATLAS

The Association for Tourism and Leisure Education and Research (ATLAS) was established in 1991 to develop transnational educational initiatives in tourism and leisure.

ATLAS provides a forum to promote staff and student exchange, transnational research and to facilitate curriculum and professional development. It currently has 155 members in 54 countries worldwide.

What are the objectives of ATLAS?

- To promote the teaching of tourism, leisure and related subjects.
- To encourage academic exchange between member institutions.
- To promote links between professional bodies in tourism, leisure and associated subjects and to liaise on educational issues, curriculum development and professional recognition of courses.
- To promote transnational research which helps to underpin the development of appropriate curricula for transnational education.

What does ATLAS do?

ATLAS promotes links between member institutions through regular meetings, publications and information exchange. The main activities of ATLAS currently are:

- Organising conferences on issues in tourism and leisure education and research. Recent international conferences have been held in Cork, Ireland (2022), in Bad Gleichenberg, Austria (2023), Breda, Netherlands (2024) and Vila-seca, Spain (2025). Regional conferences are also held in Africa (most recently in Eldoret, Kenya in 2017 and in Kampala, Uganda in 2019), in Latin America (most recently in Bogota, Columbia in 2022 and in Guerrero, Mexico in 2024) and in the Asia-Pacific region (most recently in Hanoi, Vietnam in 2023 and in Haikou, China in 2025).
- Information services and publications, including the ATLAS website, the annual ATLAS Reflections, Facebook, LinkedIn and YouTube.
- Organisation of and participation in transnational research projects, for example on cultural tourism, sustainable tourism, and information technology. ATLAS is currently participating in the CROCUS Horizon Project on cultural and creative tourism, which aims to generating knowledge about innovative cultural and creative tourism business models for different types of heritage and rural areas.
- Research publications and reports.

What are the benefits of the ATLAS membership?

- Regular mailings of information, updates on ATLAS conferences, meetings, projects, publications and other activities.
- Participation in the ATLAS mailing information list for everyone within ATLAS member institutions, as well as for the different Special Interest Groups.
- The annual ATLAS international conference, which provides an opportunity to network with other members.
- Conferences organised by regional sections.
- ATLAS members can participate in a wide range of projects run by ATLAS in the areas of tourism and leisure education and research.
- Members have access to research information gathered through ATLAS
- International projects.
- ATLAS members are listed on the ATLAS website, giving teachers and students easy access to information about member institutions via Internet.
- Distribution of information about member events, programmes, projects and products via the ATLAS mailing list and ATLAS website.
- ATLAS members are entitled to substantial discounts on ATLAS conference fees and selected ATLAS publications.
- Contacts and lobbying through ATLAS links with other international organisations.
- Opportunity for students to take part in an established academic and research network.

ATLAS Special Interest Groups

Members of ATLAS can form and join Special Interest Groups related to specific education and research topics or for specific geographical areas. Special Interest Groups run research programmes and can organise special events and publications related to their area of interest. The current Special Interest Groups are:

- | | |
|-------------------------------|-------------------------------|
| - Cultural Tourism | - Circular Economy |
| - Gastronomy and Tourism | - Artificial Intelligence and |
| - Business Tourism | Robotics in Tourism and |
| - Events | Hospitality |
| - Volunteer Tourism | - Animals in Tourism, |
| - Heritage Tourism and | Hospitality and Leisure |
| Education | - Dark Tourism |
| - Space, Place, Mobilities in | - Systems Thinking in |
| Tourism | Tourism |
| - Urban Tourism | - Medical Tourism |
| - Visual Tourism | - Orphanage Tourism |
| - Climate Change and | - Children in Tourism |
| Tourism | - Regenerative Tourism |
| - Tourism Education | |

ATLAS Regional Sections

ATLAS is also represented at regional and local level by sections such as ATLAS Europe, ATLAS Asia-Pacific, ATLAS Africa and ATLAS Latin America. The regional sections of ATLAS have developed their own programme of activities and publications to respond more closely to the specific needs of members located in these regions and those with related research interests. Membership of ATLAS regional sections and Special Interest Groups of ATLAS is open to all ATLAS members at no extra costs.

The ATLAS publication series

As a networking organisation, one of the main tasks of ATLAS is to disseminate information on developments in tourism and leisure as widely as possible. The ATLAS publication series contains volumes of selected papers from ATLAS conferences and reports from ATLAS research projects. The ATLAS Tourism and Leisure Review gives ATLAS members and participants of the ATLAS conferences and meetings a platform to publish the papers they have presented. The editing will be carried out by an editorial board / field editors.

Join ATLAS

ATLAS membership is open to bona-fide educational institutions and professional bodies with educational, research or professional interests in tourism, leisure and related areas. If your institution is interested, complete the application form on the ATLAS homepage at <https://atlas-euro.org/about/membership/>.

How much does the ATLAS membership cost?

The annual membership fee will be based on GDP per capita of the country where the member institution is based. The following tiers and fees are currently applicable:

ATLAS fee structure 2025 in EURO	
GDP > 30000	375
15000 < GDP < 30000	250
5000 < GDP < 15000	150
GDP < 5000	50

Secretariat address

ATLAS
Association for Tourism and Leisure
Education and Research

PO Box 109
6800 AC Arnhem
The Netherlands

E-mail: info@atlas-euro.org

URL: www.atlas-euro.org

ATLAS Tourism and Leisure Review

ATLAS Review Volume 2016 – 1
Well-Being and Employment in Tourism

ATLAS Review Volume 2016 – 2
Culture, Tourism and Wellbeing

ATLAS Review Volume 2016 – 3
Health, Wellness and Spa Tourism in the Balkans

ATLAS Review Volume 2017 – 1
Well-Being and Quality of Life in Tourism

ATLAS Review Volume 2017 – 2
ATLAS Africa, conference proceedings 2015

ATLAS Review Volume 2017 – 3
Tourism and Risk

ATLAS Review Volume 2018 – 1
Destinations past, present and future

ATLAS Review Volume 2018 – 2
ATLAS Africa, conference proceedings 2017

ATLAS Review Volume 2019 – 1
Dark Tourism and Higher Education

ATLAS Review Volume 2019 – 2
Destination Dynamics

ATLAS Review Volume 2019 – 3
Gastronomy and Tourism: Reflections on local food consumption in urban and rural areas

ATLAS Review Volume 2020 – 1
ATLAS Africa, conference proceedings 2019

ATLAS Review Volume 2020 – 2
Tourism and the Corona crisis: Some ATLAS reflections

ATLAS Review Volume 2020 – 3
Cultural Heritage in East Asia

ATLAS Review Volume 2022 – 1
Tourism and the Corona crisis: Some ATLAS reflections 2

ATLAS Review Volume 2024 – 1
Thesis prize winners 2023 & Prague Papers 2020 – 2021

ATLAS Review Volume 2025 – 1
Thesis prize winners 2024 & Papers Bad Gleichenberg 2023

ATLAS Review Volume 2025 – 2
Sustainable Cultural Tourism in China

ATLAS Review Volume 2026 – 1
Creativity, Economy and Tourism

**For more information please visit the
ATLAS homepage at:
www.atlas-euro.org**

